

Long-Term Water Quality
Monitoring in the Lost Creek
Watershed: A Data Synthesis

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July 25, 1994

Long-Term Water Quality Monitoring in the Lost Creek Watershed: A Data Synthesis

Prepared for

The Defiance Soil and Water Conservation District,
The U.S. Soil Conservation Service,
The Ohio Environmental Protection Agency, and
The Ohio Department of Natural Resources

July 25, 1994

Submitted by

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Assembled from component files, in some cases with reconstructed
components, by R. Peter Richards, June 2003

FORWARD

Detailed measurements of the export of sediment, nutrients and pesticides from the Lost Creek Watershed began in 1981 and extended for 12 years through September, 1993. This monitoring station is one of a network of similar stations within the Lake Erie Basin that is operated by the Water Quality Laboratory of Heidelberg College. The network currently includes stations on the River Raisin, the Maumee River, the Sandusky River and two of its tributaries (Rock Creek and Honey Creek), the Cuyahoga River, and the Grand River.

The monitoring program for the Lost Creek Watershed was designed to evaluate the effects of changing farming practices within the watershed on the export of sediments, fertilizers and pesticides from the watershed. During the monitoring period, two major efforts took place to gain farmer adoption of various conservation measures -- the Lost Creek Demonstration Project (1981-1984) and the Lost Creek 319 Project (1990 - 1993).

This report describes the water quality data that we have collected during the 12 year monitoring effort in this watershed. The data are interpreted both in terms of trends in pollutant export from the watershed and in terms of comparisons of pollutant export from the Lost Creek Watershed with export from other stations in the network. The effects of the programs to gain farmer adoption of conservation measures are also summarized in the report.

The Lost Creek data sets should prove to be very useful for a variety of future investigations. For example, the data could be very useful in testing agricultural runoff models. The current report by no means exhausts the potential for fruitful analysis of the data sets. Indeed the current report poses a number of important questions that should be addressed either by additional analysis of existing data or by the collection of additional data within the watershed.

I hope that this report will contribute to the growing body of knowledge regarding the study of agricultural watersheds and the assessment of impacts of agricultural pollution abatement programs.

David B. Baker
Director, Water Quality Laboratory

July 27, 1994

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This report summarizes 12 years of detailed water quality monitoring studies in the Lost Creek Watershed of Defiance County, Ohio. As with most long term studies, many organizations have been involved in providing support for the program. Key among these has been the Defiance Soil and Water District. They provided monitoring contracts to our laboratory as part of their Lost Creek Demonstration Project, funded by the U.S. EPA's Great Lakes National Program Office, and again as part of their Section 319 Grant, funded by the Ohio Environmental Protection Agency, the Ohio Department of Natural Resources, and Region 5 of the U.S. EPA. Major support was also received from the Soil Conservation Service for the five year period between the grants to the Defiance Soil and Water District.

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The cooperation of the Agricultural Research Service in the design and installation of the flume at the watershed outlet is greatly appreciated, as is the cooperation of the U.S. Geological Survey in the subsequent stream gauging program at the station.

Long-term monitoring studies such as this one would not have been possible without the dedicated work of staff of the Water Quality Laboratory. My thanks go to Jack Kramer, our laboratory manager, and to Ellen Ewing and Barbara Merryfield, who handled both the field operations and collections, as well as all of the laboratory analyses. Pete Richards constantly updated the computer programs used to analyze the data. Finally, my thanks go to Nancy Creamer for producing the tables and figures, proofreading, and handling this reports final production.

The contents of this report reflect the data presentations and interpretations of staff of the Heidelberg Water Quality Laboratory, and do not necessarily reflect the views of any of the sponsoring and supporting organizations.

Part 1. INTRODUCTION

For twelve years, the Water Quality Laboratory (WQL) of Heidelberg College has conducted detailed water quality studies on a small unnamed tributary within the Lost Creek watershed in Defiance County, Ohio. These studies have included measurements of the concentrations and loads of sediments, nutrients and pesticides. Within this period, two special efforts have been made to accelerate farmer adoption of practices and programs to reduce agricultural nonpoint pollution in the study watershed. This report provides a detailed description of the water quality data collected during the twelve year period, and interprets these data in relation to changing farming practices within the watershed and in relation to similar water quality data collected in the Lake Erie basin from watersheds with different sizes and physical characteristics, but with similar land uses.

A. Characteristics of the Study Watershed

The study area comprises a 4.23 square mile (2,831 acre) watershed located in Milford Township in the northwestern portion of Defiance County (Figure 1). The watershed occupies portions of sections 13, 14, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 35 and 38. It is drained by an unnamed second order tributary to Lost Creek. Water quality studies were conducted at a stream gauging station at the watershed outlet located about 400 ft. upstream from the bridge on Rosedale Rd. (lat. 40 56' 55" and long. 84 15' 58"). The United States Geological Survey (USGS) operates the gauging station (Number 04185440) and additional information regarding the site is available in USGS publications such as their annual *Water Resources Data - Ohio* publications.

The entire watershed is located within the Fort Wayne End Moraine of the Wisconsin glacial stage. As such, the watershed has more relief and higher gross erosion rates than in watersheds draining the ground moraines and lake plains that make up the majority of the northwestern Ohio drainage to Lake Erie. These end moraines have been viewed as critical sediment source areas within the Lake Erie Basin (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, 1979).

In 1987, detailed land use analysis within the watershed was conducted by the U. S. Soil Conservation Service (SCS). Their studies indicated the following (unpublished data provided by Robert Burris, Soil Conservation Service, Columbus, Ohio).

DEFIANCE COUNTY - LOST CREEK DEMONSTRATION PROJECT

Figure 1. Location of the Lost Creek Watershed in Defiance County.

81.9%	cropland
2.6%	farmsteads
10.4 %	woodland
2.4%	wasteland or brush
2.7%	ditches and roadways

In the same year, the SCS also calculated the average gross erosion rate in the watershed, using the universal soil loss equation. With the conservation practices in place in 1987, average cropland erosion was calculated to be 4.01 tons per acre per year.

Although the study watershed is located on an unnamed tributary within the Lost Creek watershed, for the sake of brevity, the study watershed will be referred to as the Lost Creek Watershed and the sampling and stream gauging station as the Lost Creek Station. Lost Creek drains into the Tiffin River, which, in turn, empties into the Maumee River.

B. Agricultural Pollution Abatement Programs in the Lost Creek Watershed

1. 1981 to 1984 - The EPA/GLNPO Lost Creek Demonstration Project - The Defiance Soil and Water Conservation District received a demonstration grant from the Great Lakes National Program Office (GLNPO) of the EPA in 1981. That grant included a program to foster adoption of conservation tillage practices in the Lost Creek Watershed, largely through the use of cash incentives and provision of conservation tillage equipment. Major efforts to gain farmer adoption of conservation practices were deferred until 1983 and 1984 so that one year of baseline water quality data could be obtained prior to initiation of changes in conservation practices. This grant also included funding to initiate and operate the water quality monitoring program at Lost Creek through the conclusion of the 1984 water year. A program of annual, field-by-field tracking of agricultural management practices within the watershed was also initiated. Details of the Lost Creek Demonstration Project are contained within the final project report to the Great Lakes National Program Office (Rettig, 1987). Results of the water quality studies for the 1982, 1983 and 1984 water years were described in the project report submitted to the Defiance Soil and Water District by Baker (1986).

2. 1985 to 1989 - The SCS Special Monitoring Project - During the period from 1985 through 1989, the SCS supported a continuation of the water quality monitoring program at the Lost Creek Station by the Water Quality Laboratory . The SCS also

supported a continuation of the annual field-by-field tracking of agricultural management practices, including tillage practices and residue-management, fertilizer application rates, and pesticide use. SCS staff applied the AGNPS model to the watershed. During this five year period, no special programs were in place within the Lost Creek watershed to foster farmer adoption of conservation practices. Hence this time interval provided an opportunity to assess whether the high rates of conservation tillage achieved in 1984 would continue or whether farmers would revert to earlier practices. Also, the impacts of area-wide educational efforts to gain farmer adoption of conservation measures could be reflected in the data. An interim water quality data report was produced in 1988 (Baker 1988a) that included a re-evaluation of the entire water quality data set dating back to 1982.

3. 1990 to 1993 - U.S. EPA Section 319 Project - The Upper Lost Creek Watershed

Project - The Farm Bills of 1985 and 1990 included several provisions to reduce agricultural nonpoint pollution, including the Conservation Reserve Program (CRP) and the conservation compliance requirements for participation in federal crop programs. Because of the relatively high gross erosion rates in the Lost Creek Watershed, programs under the Food Security Act had the potential to have a significant impact in the watershed. The Section 319 grant used the conservation compliance and CRP provisions of the Food Security Act to accelerate farmer adoption of conservation measures in the watershed. Unlike the initial Lost Creek Demonstration Project, the 319 grant contained no funds to subsidize farmer adoption of conservation measures. The 319 grant did provide limited funds to continue the tracking and monitoring programs in the watershed. Unfortunately, no funds were provided to integrate the implementation, tracking and monitoring program or to produce an integrated report.

Part 2. STUDY METHODS

A. Tracking of Conservation Practices

The Lost Creek Watershed contains approximately 90 fields, many of which were subdivided. These fields were numbered on aerial photographs of the watershed. Staff of the Defiance Soil and Water Conservation District conducted annual interviews with farmers to determine the cropping practices on each field. During the initial four years of the project, information collected on each field was limited to the tillage management and crop. Subsequent surveys added information on nutrient and pesticide use. A copy of the form used for the farmer surveys during the last three years of the project is shown in the appendix to this report.

For the period from 1986 to 1989, data from the individual fields were entered into an SCS microcomputer and stored in PFS:First Choice files. For the period between 1990 and 1992, field sheets were transferred to the WQL where the data were placed into FilemakerPro.2.0 files for storage and summarization. The tracking program was not operated in 1993. The WQL obtained the SCS files and added them to the FilemakerPro.2.0 files. The original data sheets for the 1982-1984 period are no longer available and only the summaries are available, as reported in the project report (Rettig, 1987). All field sheets from 1986 through 1992 are stored at the WQL.

A farmer network or rainfall data in the watershed had been in operation during much of the project. Portions of these data are stored in computer format and other rainfall data is stored on original report sheets. The rainfall data has not been reviewed as a part of this report.

B. Discharge Measurements

To facilitate the measurement of discharge from the watershed, a trapezoidal flume designed by the Agricultural Research Service (ARS) was installed at the watershed outlet (Figure 2). A stilling well and gauge house were installed adjacent to the flume. The ARS provided a theoretical rating table for the flume for converting stages to discharges.

During the initial four years of the project, the WQL monitored the stage data using an Isco pressure transducer system. Stages were recorded at 15 minute intervals. The WQL used

Figure 2. Trapezoidal flume used for discharge measurements at the Lost Creek gauging station.

procedures similar to those of the USGS for determining daily discharges. During this time, a theoretical rating curve was used to calculate discharges. Beginning with the 1986 water year, the station was added to the USGS network of discharge stations for Ohio. Grant funds of the WQL were passed through the Seneca Soil and Water Conservation District to provide the matching funds for the USGS cooperative program. The USGS initiated stream discharge measurements to develop a rating curve for the station. They also installed a floating sensor for measuring stages in the stilling well. This replaced the pressure transducer used by the WQL up to that time. Annual discharge data for the station have subsequently been published by the USGS in their series on *Water Resources Data: Ohio*.

C. Water Sampling Procedures

Water samples for nutrient and sediment analyses were collected at the gauging site using two ISCO Model 1680 water samplers. One sampler was used to collect samples at 6 hour intervals on a continuing basis. The second sampler was set to trigger on a rising stage and collect hourly samples for 28 hours. Staff from the Defiance County SWCD changed the second sampler base after runoff events so that hourly samples could be collected from multiple events during a single week. A printer was connected to the hourly sampler so that the time of sample collection was recorded for each bottle. WQL staff visited the station on a weekly basis throughout the years. At each visit the sampler bases were exchanged. Grab samples were periodically taken for quality control programs, including studies of the effects of sample storage and for comparisons between grab and pumped samples.

Under low flow conditions prior to 1985, the water level in the flume dropped below the intake tube for the sampler pumps. Consequently, under low flow conditions, characterization of the stream chemistry was based on the weekly grab samples. In 1985, a submersible pump was installed which continuously pumped water into the gauge house. This allowed the automatic samplers to collect four samples per day even under low flow conditions. Typically, one sample per day is analyzed to characterize low flow stream chemistry. The absence of daily low flow samples in the 1982-1984 does not affect the export data from the watershed.

Samples for pesticide analyses were collected with an ISCO Model 2100 Pesticide Sampler. The sampler was set to collect two samples per day for the period from mid-April

through August. Each sample required two bottles to provide sufficient sample volume for pesticide analyses. Since the sampler only contains 24 bottles, the pesticide sampler would only cover a six day interval. WQL staff also collected grab samples for pesticide analyses during their weekly visits to the sampling station. Beginning in about 1986, pesticide samples were also collected twice per month for the September to mid-April period.

D. Analytical Methods - Nutrients and Sediments

The analytical methods used by the WQL for nutrients and sediments are summarized in Table 1. The nutrient methods reflect standard automated colorimetric procedures, using methods set forth in *Methods for Analysis of Water and Wastes*, U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, Monitoring and Support Laboratory, Cincinnati, Ohio (EPA 600/4-79-020). The WQL operates under quality control programs that have been approved by both the U.S. EPA and the USGS.

E. Analytical Methods - Pesticides

For the period between 1983 and 1992, all pesticide analyses were conducted using gas chromatography. Samples were extracted with methylene chloride, concentrated in Kuderna-Danish glassware, and analyzed using dual column capillary chromatography coupled with nitrogen-phosphorus thermionic detectors. The method employed was essentially that of EPA Draft Method 507. In 1993, the WQL switched to analysis by gas chromatography - mass spectroscopy. Also, in 1993, the WQL switched to solid phase extraction. The methods currently employed are those described in EPA Method 525.1 Revision 2.2 (EPA 1991). Additional descriptions of the pesticide analytical procedures are contained in various WQL publications (Kramer and Baker, 1985; Baker, 1988b; and Richards and Baker, 1992)

F. Data Storage

All analytical data are transferred to the WQL's mainframe computer (VAX 750) for storage and subsequent analysis. Beginning in 1989, all data transfers between the analytical equipment and the mainframe computer were automated. Prior to that time, analytical results were manually entered into the data storage system.

Table 1. Methods and equipment used in the WQL's analytical program for surface and ground waters.

Group/Parameter	Analytical Equipment	Method ID from EPA-600/4-79-020 or listed EPA reference
Inorganics (run on all surface water samples beginning in 1974, and, except for #1-#3, on all well samples)		
1. Total Suspended Solids	Mettler balances	EPA Method 160.2
2. Total Phosphorus	Technicon Autoanalyzer II	EPA Method 365.3
3. Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen	Technicon Autoanalyzer II	EPA Method 351.1
4. Nitrate + nitrite nitrogen	TRAACs Autoanalyzer	EPA Method 353.2
5. Nitrite nitrogen	TRAACs Autoanalyzer	EPA Method 353.2
6. Ammonia	TRAACs Autoanalyzer	EPA Method 350.1
7. Chloride	TRAACs Autoanalyzer	EPA Method 352.2
8. Soluble reactive phosphorus	TRAACs Autoanalyzer	EPA Method 365.2
9. Sulfate	TRAACs Autoanalyzer	EPA Method 375.2
10. Silica	TRAACs Autoanalyzer	EPA Method 370.1
11. Specific Conductance	TRAACs Autoanalyzer	EPA Method 120.1
Current Generation Pesticides (started in 1982 on selected surface water samples; immunoassay testing on selected well water samples.)		
1. Via Solid Phase Extraction & GC/MS 16 pesticides routinely included	Varian Saturn II GC/MS	EPA Method 525.1 Revision 2.2 EPA/4-88/039
2. Via immunoassay (EnviroGard™ plate kits for quantitative studies of triazines, Lasso, 2,4 D, & others)	FisherBioteck Microkinetics Reader	
Volatile Organic Chemicals (including THMS) (on selected wells and rivers, beginning 1992)		
1. Via Automated Purge and Trap followed by GC/MS 50 + compounds including trihalomethanes	Varian Saturn II GC/MS & Tekmar ALS 2050/LSC 2000	EPA Method 524.2 EPA/4-88/039 (Revised 1991)
Metals (including major cations and trace metals, selected river samples beginning 1992)		
1. Via sequential ICP Ca, Mg, Na, K, Sr, Ba, Al, Fe, Ag, Ni, Mn, Cr, Zn, Cu, Cd, Pb, Co, Sb	Varian Liberty 100 ICP w/ ultrasonic nebulizer	EPA Method 200.7 Revision 3.3 (4/91) EPA/600/4-91/010

In addition to the analytical results for each sample, the sampling location, date and time, stream stage at the time of sample collection, and stream discharge are added to the computer files. Thus all data for the Lost Creek Station, as well as the other stations operated by the WQL, are available in electronic format.

G. Data Analysis

The WQL has developed a useful set of computer programs that aid in the interpretation of data collected in tributary monitoring programs. The major computer programs that have been used in analysis of Lost Creek data, as well as for data from other stations, are described below. Representative printouts from the computer programs are also shown.

1. Archive Printout - The archive program generates a tabular summary of the nutrient and sediment data as illustrated in Figure 3. The operator selects the station and enters the beginning date and ending date. The resulting output tables show all of the data available at that station between the beginning and ending dates. The outputs are useful for examining individual storm events or periods of missing information.

2. Flux Program - The flux program calculates nutrient and sediment loads using the USGS mid-interval technique. In this technique, the instantaneous discharge and concentration are used to characterize stream loading for the time period extending half way between that sample and the previous sample and half way between that sample and the following sample. The instantaneous discharge is determined by the stage at the time of sample collection, as provided by interim USGS stage data, and the applicable rating table data, also provided by the USGS. The program allows the operator to set the maximum duration of time that a single sample can be used to characterize the flux rate. A representative output from the program is shown in Figure 4. The operator selects the station and parameter and then inserts the starting and ending times and the maximum time window either side of the sample. In addition to the loads, the program indicates the total volume (discharge) during the time interval, the mean flow, the elapsed time and the monitored time, several forms of average concentrations (normal average, flux weighted average, time weighted average) and the number of samples processed during the time interval.

3. Exceedency Program - The exceedency program provides a means of analyzing the concentrations of nutrients, sediments and pesticides. It includes both a tabular output

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WATER QUALITY LAB
MAJOR NUTRIENTS AND SEDIMENTS

HEIDELBERG COLLEGE

TIFFIN

OHIO

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PAGE 1

station : datetime	Mult hrs	Flow cfs	Stage ft	TP- P mg/l	TSP- P mg/l	SRP- P mg/l	SS mg/l	N023- N mg/l	NH3- N mg/l	TKN- N mg/l	Cond umhos
9301010100	0.000	17.69	2.19	0.145	-9.000	0.020	31.	0.30	0.084	0.697	412.
9301271900	0.000	2.30	1.57	0.101	-9.000	0.015	33.	2.25	0.078	0.882	498.
9301281900	0.000	7.64	1.88	0.151	-9.000	0.018	42.	1.59	0.093	1.083	458.
9301291900	0.000	2.75	1.61	0.213	-9.000	0.047	41.	1.83	0.096	1.037	384.
9301301900	0.000	1.88	1.53	0.107	-9.000	0.017	15.	2.06	0.088	0.832	504.
9301311900	0.000	1.78	1.52	0.071	-9.000	0.016	12.	2.14	0.094	0.747	539.
9302010700	0.000	1.88	1.53	0.108	-9.000	0.022	21.	1.66	0.116	0.887	482.
9302011300	0.000	1.35	1.47	0.117	-9.000	0.021	32.	1.77	0.126	0.880	479.
9302021300	0.000	1.06	1.43	0.090	-9.000	0.015	16.	2.05	0.118	0.757	553.
9302031300	0.000	0.91	1.41	0.066	-9.000	0.013	12.	2.13	0.119	0.649	593.
9302041300	0.000	0.84	1.40	0.057	-9.000	0.014	9.	1.92	0.164	0.576	616.
9302051300	0.000	0.91	1.41	0.047	-9.000	0.010	8.	2.05	0.130	0.515	612.
9302061300	0.000	0.91	1.41	0.060	-9.000	0.011	13.	1.83	0.125	0.615	581.
9302071300	0.000	0.79	1.39	0.049	-9.000	0.009	13.	2.05	0.119	0.505	612.
9302080700	0.000	0.79	1.39	0.044	-9.000	0.009	8.	2.02	0.127	0.557	602.
9302081300	0.000	0.75	1.38	0.052	-9.000	0.008	11.	2.07	0.053	0.330	632.
9302091300	0.000	0.70	1.37	0.040	-9.000	0.008	12.	2.03	0.071	0.217	662.
9302101300	0.000	0.66	1.36	0.033	-9.000	0.008	10.	2.02	0.080	0.149	670.
9302111300	0.000	0.70	1.37	0.035	-9.000	0.008	7.	1.96	0.073	0.079	675.
9302121300	0.000	0.79	1.39	0.031	-9.000	0.008	11.	1.99	0.079	0.054	648.
9302131300	0.000	0.70	1.37	0.027	-9.000	0.005	8.	1.95	0.093	0.057	652.
9302141300	0.000	0.70	1.37	0.030	-9.000	0.005	7.	1.85	0.086	0.057	668.
9302150700	0.000	0.79	1.39	0.039	-9.000	0.010	10.	1.82	0.114	0.104	669.
9302151300	0.000	0.70	1.37	0.033	-9.000	0.004	6.	1.70	0.066	0.616	641.
9302161300	0.000	0.66	1.36	0.034	-9.000	0.005	8.	1.78	0.074	0.627	655.
9302171300	0.000	0.66	1.36	0.039	-9.000	0.007	9.	1.69	0.066	0.565	680.
9302181300	0.000	0.56	1.34	0.028	-9.000	0.005	12.	1.90	0.071	0.619	736.
9302191300	0.000	0.56	1.34	0.022	-9.000	0.003	10.	2.11	0.076	0.867	792.
9302201300	0.000	0.56	1.34	0.018	-9.000	0.001	7.	1.91	0.064	0.496	731.
9302211300	0.000	0.66	1.36	0.017	-9.000	0.003	3.	1.81	0.067	0.619	717.
9302220700	0.000	0.70	1.37	0.020	-9.000	0.004	4.	1.81	0.096	0.471	702.
9302221300	0.000	0.66	1.36	0.015	-9.000	0.005	6.	1.66	0.095	0.587	636.

Figure 3. Sample of Archive Program printout.

Flux summary for Defiance

Dates between 9303010000 and 9303310000

Parameter: TP

Total load in metric tons	:	.309762
in short tons	:	.341358
Total volume in cubic meters	:	.105287E+07
in cfs-days	:	430.269
Mean flow in cubic meters per second:		.413058
in cubic feet per second	:	14.5854
Monitored time in days	:	29.5
Elapsed time in days	:	30
Mean concentration in mg/L	:	.209919
Flux weighted concentration in mg/L	:	.294208
Time weighted concentration in mg/L	:	.184149
Number of samples processed	:	69
Maximum time window either side of a sample is		1 days

Figure 4. Sample of Flux Program printout.

(Figure 5) and a graphical output (Figure 6). The operator selects the station and parameter, and indicates the starting and ending times. The operator also selects the maximum time that a sample is used to characterize the stream concentration and how to deal with missing time. Missing time can either be ignored or assigned a specific value. The tabular output provides both the flow and time weighted average concentrations, as well as the median, various percentiles (90th, 95th and 99th), the maximum, and minimum. The graphical output can be used to assess the percentage of time that concentrations fall within any range or the percentage of time a given concentration is exceeded.

4. Flow Ratio Program - The flow ratio program is used to calculate annual water year loads for nutrient and sediment parameters (Figure 7). It applies a flux program calculation to each month of the water year using a maximum time window of 0.5 days on either side of any sample. Final USGS flow data for each month are entered into separate files accessed by the program. The program then calculates the ratio of the USGS flow divided by the observed flow from our sampling program. Because the USGS final monthly flow data includes both a finer resolution of the daily flows (i.e. it uses hourly or 15 minute stage values) and includes any adjustments to the daily discharge made by the USGS (e.g., for winter ice conditions) the USGS flows are taken as the best available estimate of monthly discharge. The program then calculates a revised flux for each month by multiplying the observed flux by the flow ratio.

In practice, the output from the flow ratio becomes a worksheet for manual calculations of the final annual loads. If the flow ratios deviate significantly from 1 for a given month, manual corrections are made to the monthly load. Where the sampling program missed a considerable amount of time and/or flow in a given month, as indicated by the cumulative time for the sampling program each month and the flow ratio, the missing load during the missing flow is manually calculated. A concentration equivalent to the long term flux weighted concentration for that month is multiplied by the missing flow, and the resulting load is added to the observed load for the portion of time the sampling program did operate in that month. These corrections are done for each parameter and for each month where adjustments affect the final annual load by more than 1%. The annual loads reported in this report and its appendices have been adjusted in this fashion. The final flow ratio worksheets are in storage at the WQL.

River: [RIVER]DEFIAind.dat

Parameter: N03

Total number of samples: 4415
Initial sample used: 8510010000
Final sample used: 9309302400
Elapsed time between initial and final samples: 2922.000 days
Total time represented by samples: 2575.800 days
Time not represented by samples: 346.200 days
Maximum time a sample represents: 2.000 days
69 samples had no flow
These samples represented 40.375 days

DISTRIBUTION CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DATA

All concentrations are given in milligrams per liter

Time-weighted mean concentration: 2.731
Flow-weighted mean concentration: 3.960
Median concentration (50% percentile): 2.040 (at 49.97th percentile)
90th percentile concentration: 5.540 (at 89.98th percentile)
95th percentile concentration: 7.650 (at 94.98th percentile)
99th percentile concentration: 12.900 (at 98.98th percentile)
Minimum concentration: 0.000
Maximum concentration: 30.100

Conditions imposed on this run:

Data used: data between 8510010000 and 9309302400

Handling of missing time: missing time ignored.

Samples with missing flows were excluded from calculation of the FVMC

Figure 5. Sample of Exceedency Program printout.

Figure 6. Concentration exceedency curve for nitrate levels in Lost Creek from 1986-1993 produced using the Concentration Exceedency Program.

Flux Comparison for [RIVER]DEFIAind.dat
 Parameter: TP
 Water year: 1993

Month	N	FWMC mg/L	Cum. Time days	Obs. Flow m**3	USGS Flow m**3	Flow Ratio	Obs. Flux Metric Tons	Calc. Flux Metric Tons
Oct.	41	.863814	28.75	229124	180368	.787207	.197921	.155805
Nov.	40	.471258	17.75	915915	.114838E+07	1.2538	.431632	.541182
Dec.	61	.513781	30.25	691027	618210	.894625	.355036	.317625
Jan.	6	.114409	5.29199	62175.8	.105074E+07	16.8995	.711345E-02	.120214
Feb.	32	.414894E-01	28.042	51777.5	39054.1	.754268	.214822E-02	.162033E-02
Mar.	70	.335994	30.875	.106464E+07	997275	.936721	.357714	.335078
Apr.	64	.515812	21.4834	540421	577492	1.0686	.278756	.297878
May	49	.278605	30.75	172749	127073	.735593	.481285E-01	.035403
June	70	.280116	27	245114	242693	.990124	.686603E-01	.679822E-01
July	30	.913453E-01	27.5	124103	125605	1.0121	.113362E-01	.114734E-01
Aug.	36	.405693E-01	31	8424.13	5750.45	.682616	.341761E-03	.233292E-03
Sept.	36	.244852	29.479	37720.2	32985.6	.874479	.923588E-02	.807658E-02
	-----		-----	-----	-----		-----	-----
	535	.426729	308.171	.41432E+07	.514563E+07		1.76802	1.89257
Adjusted FWMC:		.367802						

Figure 7. Sample of printout from Flow Ratio Program.

5. Monthly Concentration Summary Program - This program calculates the monthly flow weighted and time weighted concentrations for major nutrient and sediment parameters and indicates the number of samples used in the calculation (Figure 8). The operator chooses the station and the starting and ending dates. Thus the program would list the average concentrations observed during all of the Januarys occurring between the starting and ending dates. These concentrations are used in correcting the monthly loads when there is missing data, as described above. A version of the monthly average concentration program is also available for pesticides, but it does not include a calculation of the flow weighted mean concentration.

6. Automated Beale Ratio Estimator Program - Because pesticide analyses are completed on fewer samples than are nutrient analyses, a different technique is used to calculate annual pesticide loads. The technique involves application of the Beale Ratio Estimator, as used by the International Joint Commission and others. Under a grant from the EPA's Great Lakes National Program Office (GLNPO), the WQL has automated the application of the technique in such a way that the available data is stratified to minimize the standard error associated with the loading estimate. Details of the method are contained in the final report to GLNPO, which is currently in preparation by R. Peter Richards of our laboratory.

7. Annual Chemograph Program - A program is available to extract data from the data files and plot water year chemographs as presented in Appendix A. The program plots chemographs in a six panel format including the annual hydrograph, as well as chemographs for suspended solids, total phosphorus, soluble reactive phosphorus, nitrate plus nitrite nitrogen, and conductivity. The program automatically scales the loading axes (Y-axis), and the scales shift from year to year for each parameter.

H. Data Availability

All of the tracking, flow, and chemical data described in this report is stored in electronic media and can be made available for distribution to other users. Those interested in obtaining portions of the data should contact the WQL to arrange for data transfer. Costs for the data sets would be limited to the labor and material costs for transferring the records.

Average concentrations for [RIVER]DEFIAind.dat
 For dates between 8410010000 and 9209300000

Produced by the program [RIVER.MARK]MONTHLY_AVES

		Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
SS	FWMC:	190.155	86.599	402.963	443.378	561.523	318.898	542.697	352.155	144.981	226.326	114.138	192.272
	TWMC:	32.127	27.993	61.039	63.821	55.405	71.345	68.031	31.929	18.813	23.895	24.869	35.756
	n:	235	347	507	453	368	384	332	248	237	320	391	429
TP	FWMC:	0.339	0.250	0.600	0.667	0.764	0.431	0.754	0.514	0.387	0.456	0.337	0.468
	TWMC:	0.133	0.133	0.159	0.146	0.119	0.145	0.151	0.094	0.088	0.104	0.113	0.139
	n:	236	348	507	453	366	385	332	238	230	323	393	430
SRP	FWMC:	0.033	0.033	0.024	0.026	0.044	0.027	0.054	0.056	0.079	0.093	0.050	0.048
	TWMC:	0.016	0.022	0.013	0.027	0.017	0.019	0.031	0.018	0.021	0.024	0.019	0.018
	n:	219	328	465	417	338	367	322	240	227	306	379	368
NO3	FWMC:	3.793	3.025	3.438	2.758	6.031	5.789	5.887	2.217	2.151	5.585	6.868	4.120
	TWMC:	3.220	3.229	3.117	2.400	2.631	3.960	2.977	1.333	1.298	2.867	3.929	3.798
	n:	236	348	507	453	369	383	333	244	237	325	401	431
TKN	FWMC:	1.797	1.369	2.847	2.736	3.983	2.418	3.509	2.168	1.909	2.273	1.877	1.827
	TWMC:	0.995	0.989	1.285	1.162	1.180	1.174	1.123	0.788	0.818	0.935	1.084	0.994
	n:	235	347	506	451	369	373	324	246	237	315	393	428
CL	FWMC:	13.255	11.589	11.467	10.233	14.844	16.151	12.784	6.974	11.875	12.540	18.814	13.436
	TWMC:	19.363	17.292	15.271	14.683	17.714	18.753	17.682	16.122	18.672	21.632	23.039	20.485
	n:	236	348	507	453	369	384	334	248	230	325	401	431

Figure 8. Sample of printout from Monthly Average Program.

Part 3. RESULTS: CHANGES IN LAND MANAGEMENT IN THE LOST CREEK WATERSHED

A. Overview

The completeness of the data base upon which changes in land management can be judged has varied during the study period. In Figure 9, the number of cropland acres for which some information is available is illustrated. For the period between 1981 and 1987, information is available for between 1914 and 2106 acres each year. In 1988 records were available for only 1046 acres and in 1989 only about 1391 acres. In 1990 and 1991 information was available for 2601 and 2501 acres respectively, while in 1992 information was available for only 1639 acres. The number of cropland acres reported in 1990 and 1991 is larger than the amounts of cropland reported by the SCS in their land use analysis of the watershed. Possibly the data sheets include portions of fields not within the drainage boundary of the watershed. No tracking of management practices occurred in 1993.

It is doubtful that the actual amounts of cropland varied from year to year to the extent shown in Figure 9. It seems more likely that the tracking records were simply less complete in 1988, 1989, and 1992 than in other years. The extent to which the records for these three years may be biased is also unknown. These three years all occurred during the seven year period when efforts to record fertilizer and pesticide use were included in the tracking program. Consequently, much of the annual variability in chemical use data during the 1986 to 1992 period is likely due to incomplete records.

The acres of individual crops grown each year in the Lost Creek Watershed are shown in Table 2. The percent of the reported acres for each crop and year are also shown. Soybeans were the dominant crop followed by corn and wheat, with much smaller amounts of oats and hay.

B. Tillage Practices and the Conservation Reserve Program

Variations in no-till and CRP acres in the Lost Creek Watershed are also shown in Figure 10. No-till acres peaked in 1983 and 1984 and again in 1990, 1991, and 1992. CRP acres began to appear in 1986 and peaked in 1991. The low reported acres in 1988 and 1989 may account for the apparent drop in CRP acres in those years. In Figure 11, no-till and CRP are presented as a percent of total reported acres. As a percent of cropland acres, both

Figure 9. Annual variations in cropland reported in the tracking program

Table 2. Annual variations in acres of individual crops reported for the Lost Creek Watershed

Year	Corn	Soybeans	Wheat	Oats	Hay	Idle/CRP	Total
1982	762	1114	126		30		2032
1983	533	775	412		315		2035
1984	700	796	488		86		2070
1985	0	0	0	0	0	13	13
1986	636.7	773.8	188.1	74.9	113.1	111.7	1898.3
1987	519.7	894.3	145.7	25.1	95	366.6	2046.4
1988	207.8	232.5	249.3	0	97.9	219.8	1007.3
1989	292.1	512.5	122.1	92.7	81.3	281.4	1382.1
1990	721	697.8	403.2	16.1	85.4	494.4	2417.9
1991	581.8	792.2	345.7	18.3	87.7	593	2418.7
1992	470.4	418.6	218.1	11.4	50.1	449.4	1618.0

Figure 10. Annual variations in no-till crop acres and in CRP acres.

Figure 11. Annual variations in the percent of no-till cropland and in CRP acres.

no-till and CRP increased throughout the 1990 to 1992 period, and by 1992 together covered almost 60% of the reported cropland acres.

Primary tillage practices used in the Lost Creek Watershed for the 1986 to 1992 period are shown in Table 3. The extent of moldboard plowing decreased throughout the study period, and by 1992, only 101 acres out of 1639 cropland acres (6.2%) were plowed. In addition to no-till, chisel plow and other tillage practices were used in significant quantities. The degree of residue cover remaining after the use of the chisel and other tillage practices is not directly recorded in the data sheets.

The distribution of no-till and reduced till among various crops in the Lost Creek Watershed is shown in Tables 4 and 5 respectively. No-till was used more often in corn than in beans, while the opposite was true for reduced till. More total acres of reduced till were reported during the 1986-1992 period than of no-till. The residue levels associated with the reduced tillage category are not directly indicated, but could be estimated based on the rotation patterns in individual fields.

C. Chemical Use

Total nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium use for reported cropland acres and tons per acre cropland acre are shown in Figures 12 and 13. The data from which the graphs were plotted are shown in Table 6. In the calculation of the tons per acre, reported applications were divided by total cropland acres, including CRP acres. Application rates would have been somewhat higher if the CRP acres were subtracted from the total cropland acres.

Nitrogen fertilization rates varied considerably from year to year. This variation is affected by the variable ratios of corn to soybeans from year to year (See Table 2). Years with higher ratios of corn to soybeans had higher nitrogen application rates per acre.

Although the data files do contain application rates for many of the herbicides, the data were recorded in ways that precluded direct calculation of the amounts of active ingredients that were applied. While this information could be extracted from the files, it will require collaboration between those who collected the field data and WQL staff.

Table 3. Primary tillage practices as reported for the Lost Creek Watershed

Year	No-Till	Chisel	Plow	Other	Total Crop Acres
1982	59	17			2331
1983	429	71			2351
1984	427	316			2354
1985	0	13	0	0	13
1986	141.8	578.6	394.6	476.1	1914.6
1987	64.9	537.4	425	387.6	2105.8
1988	58.3	79.1	203.9	370.8	1045.7
1989	61.5	360.3	430.3	141.7	1391.4
1990	399.9	402.5	384.2	348.1	2601.4
1991	579	338	271.8	286.6	2500.8
1992	532.7	224.6	101.1	142.4	1639

Table 4. Annual variations in the use of no-till by crop.

Year	No-Till Corn	No-Till Beans	No-Till Wheat	Total No-Till	Total Crop Acres
1982	47	12		59	2331
1983	166	188	75	429	2351
1984	304	101	22	427	2354
1985	0	0	0	0	13
1986	101.3	40.5	0	141.8	1914.6
1987	23.8	41.1	0	64.9	2105.8
1988	19.5	38.8	0	58.3	1045.7
1989	50.5	11	0	61.5	1391.4
1990	222.5	120.3	18.4	399.9	2601.4
1991	222.6	335.5	20.9	579	2500.8
1992	289.9	189.1	53.7	532.7	1639

Table 5. Annual variations in the use of reduced till by crop.

Year	Reduced Till Corn	Reduced Till Beans	Reduced Till Wheat	Total Reduced Till	Total Crop Acres
1982	17			17	2331
1983	35	36		71	2351
1984	75	241		316	2354
1985	0	0	13	13	13
1986	169.1	281.3	72.9	578.6	1914.6
1987	202.3	315.5	19.6	537.4	2105.8
1988	36.8	21.8	20.5	79.1	1045.7
1989	84.1	205.6	39.9	360.3	1391.4
1990	157.9	205.2	38.4	402.5	2601.4
1991	130.1	141.3	66.6	338	2500.8
1992	111.1	93.2	0	224.6	1639

Table 6. Summary of reported amounts of nutrients applied as fertilizers.

Year	Nitrogen (tons)	Phosphorus (tons)	Potassium (tons)	Idle/CRP	Total Crop Acres
1986	62.15	35.54	50.55	111.7	1914.6
1987	16.20	26.32	45.16	366.6	2105.8
1988	12.04	15.80	19.58	219.8	1045.7
1989	16.65	19.24	22.39	281.4	1391.4
1990	61.36	35.25	47.36	494.4	2601.4
1991	45.89	32.81	45.80	593	2500.8
1992	35.19	21.58	31.40	449.4	1639

Figure 12. Annual variations in the reported amounts of nutrients applied

Figure 13. Annual variations in the reported amounts of nutrients applied per acre of cropland

Part 4. RESULTS: WATER QUALITY ASSESSMENTS

A. Stream Discharge

The most recent summary of the USGS discharge data for the Lost Creek gauging station is shown in Figure 14, which is a reproduction of the 1993 water year report from the USGS's *Water Resources Data: Ohio. - 1993 Water Year*. As such, the report lists the daily discharges for Lost Creek from October 1, 1992 through September 30, 1993. Similar daily flow data for the Lost Creek station have been published by the USGS beginning with the 1986 water year. For the 1982 through 1985 water years, daily discharge data have been published by the WQL in formats similar to that shown in Figure 14 (Baker, 1988a).

Annual variations in discharge for the Lost Creek watershed, as well as the seasonal characteristics of the discharge, are shown in Figure 15 for the entire period of record (WQL plus USGS data). This indicates that the highest annual discharges occurred in the early part of the period of record (1982-1985). The lowest discharge occurred in 1987.

A noteworthy aspect of the discharge data from Lost Creek is the relatively high amount of runoff from this watershed. For the USGS's period of record, the average annual discharge, as indicated by the inches of runoff from the watershed, is 15.37 inches (Figure 14). Inclusion of the WQL study period increases the annual average discharge to 18.42 inches. In Table 7, the average annual runoff for several other northwestern Ohio watersheds is listed, both for the same time interval as the Lost Creek period of record, and for the entire period of record for the station. During the 1982-1993 water years, the runoff from other northwestern Ohio streams ranged from 11.53 in. to 13.16 in. while that for Lost Creek was 18.42 inches. For all of the other stations except Honey Creek, the 1982-1993 period had higher discharges than for their entire period of record.

The 1993 USGS report (Figure 14) also lists comments on the station, as well as summary statistics for the period of record for the USGS study period. It should be noted that, under the "remarks" section, the USGS considers the records at the Lost Creek station to be fair, except estimated discharges, which are poor. The remarks section also lists the time periods during the year for which discharges were estimated. A "fair" classification indicates that 95% of the listed values are within 15% of the true value, while a "poor"

STREAMS TRIBUTARY TO LAKE ERIE

43

04185440 UNNAMED TRIBUTARY TO LOST CREEK NR FARMER, OH

LOCATION.--Lat 41°21'42", long 84°41'28", Defiance County, Hydrologic Unit 04100006, on right bank 400 ft above bridge on Rosedale Rd., 0.5 mi above mouth and 2.0 mi from Farmer.

DRAINAGE AREA.--4.23 mi².
PERIOD OF RECORD.--October 1985 to current year.

GAGE.--Water-stage recorder. Elevation of gage is 760 ft above sea level from topographic map.

REMARKS.--Estimated discharges: Dec. 10, 12-15, 22-28, Jan. 8-12, 14-18, 24 to Mar. 6, 12-14, 20-22, 25-29, May 17, June 17, July 20 to Aug. 4. Records fair, except estimated discharges, which are poor.

DISCHARGE, CUBIC FEET PER SECOND, WATER YEAR OCTOBER 1992 TO SEPTEMBER 1993
DAILY MEAN VALUES

DAY	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP
1	.31	22	1.5	11	1.2	.45	47	1.3	.71	4.4	.12	.07
2	.26	66	1.4	6.2	1.0	1.1	11	1.1	.70	5.1	.10	.87
3	.22	16	1.7	26	.94	2.5	4.8	1.1	1.1	3.5	.09	1.5
4	.20	7.6	1.3	176	.86	8.0	3.3	1.4	1.4	2.6	.08	.62
5	.18	4.6	1.0	51	.77	5.3	2.8	20	2.2	2.1	.08	.12
6	.17	3.1	.85	12	.70	4.5	2.4	3.6	3.1	1.7	.08	.95
7	.17	2.5	.81	7.7	.64	14	2.2	1.8	6.8	1.6	.10	.70
8	.41	2.1	.73	6.0	.60	37	2.1	1.2	13	2.4	.10	.13
9	27	1.6	.69	4.5	.57	31	9.9	.97	16	1.7	.09	.10
10	3.6	1.5	.67	3.0	.54	16	18	.82	9.0	2.3	.10	.10
11	2.6	11	.81	2.5	.52	7.8	4.2	3.1	4.1	2.0	.10	.09
12	1.4	118	.94	2.1	.50	6.8	3.9	1.8	2.0	3.5	.09	.09
13	.78	34	1.4	4.6	.48	5.0	2.9	.82	1.1	1.8	.09	.08
14	1.4	7.9	2.0	4.4	.47	2.5	2.3	.66	.72	1.8	.08	.08
15	3.1	5.1	2.9	3.0	.46	1.8	3.9	.53	.50	2.0	.08	3.2
16	13	3.5	29	2.2	.45	9.4	23	.66	.46	2.1	.08	.59
17	4.0	2.4	6.7	1.8	.45	33	4.8	.64	.52	1.1	.07	.17
18	1.7	1.9	3.8	1.6	.45	10	2.9	.63	.24	1.5	.07	.11
19	.97	1.6	2.5	1.5	.45	3.6	3.8	.61	.21	1.3	.07	.10
20	1.1	1.5	7.0	1.5	.44	7.0	9.3	.64	.72	1.6	.06	.09
21	4.2	2.1	2.2	18	.44	11	3.3	.89	4.2	1.1	.06	.09
22	1.8	62	1.3	37	.43	24	2.1	1.2	4.0	.78	.06	.09
23	1.1	61	1.0	14	.43	88	1.6	.84	2.6	.62	.06	.09
24	.88	10	.96	11	.44	27	1.4	.70	2.0	.51	.06	.09
25	.68	6.4	.76	5.8	.45	16	45	.60	4.1	.44	.06	.10
26	.56	4.8	.62	3.0	.43	10	8.6	.55	4.5	.43	.06	.11
27	.48	3.0	.56	2.0	.43	7.0	3.6	.63	3.8	.39	.05	.94
28	.42	2.3	.54	4.3	.42	5.0	2.3	.70	3.3	.33	.05	1.6
29	.36	2.0	1.0	2.5	---	4.5	1.8	.78	3.0	.27	.05	.36
30	.34	1.8	87	1.7	---	4.3	1.8	.92	3.1	.20	.05	.25
31	.32	---	89	1.5	---	4.0	---	.74	---	.16	.06	---
TOTAL	73.71	469.3	252.64	429.4	15.96	407.55	236.0	51.93	99.18	51.33	2.35	13.48
MEAN	2.38	15.6	8.15	13.9	.57	13.1	7.87	1.68	3.31	1.66	.076	.45
MAX	27	118	89	176	1.2	88	47	20	16	5.1	.12	3.2
MIN	.17	1.5	.54	1.5	.42	.45	1.4	.53	.21	.16	.05	.07
CFSM	.56	3.70	1.93	3.27	.13	3.11	1.86	.40	.78	.39	.02	.11
IN.	.65	4.13	2.22	3.78	.14	3.58	2.08	.46	.87	.45	.02	.12

STATISTICS OF MONTHLY MEAN DATA FOR WATER YEARS 1986 - 1993, BY WATER YEAR (WY)

	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993
MEAN	4.56	6.57	8.63	5.84	7.75	7.67	7.04	3.22
MAX	12.6	15.6	23.9	13.9	21.2	13.9	14.1	10.9
(WY)	1987	1993	1991	1993	1990	1986	1991	1990
MIN	1.4	1.53	.11	1.68	.57	3.59	1.92	.26
(WY)	1990	1990	1990	1988	1993	1989	1987	1988

SUMMARY STATISTICS	FOR 1992 CALENDAR YEAR	FOR 1993 WATER YEAR	WATER YEARS 1986 - 1993
ANNUAL TOTAL	1790.33	2102.83	
ANNUAL MEAN	4.89	5.76	4.78
HIGHEST ANNUAL MEAN			5.87
LOWEST ANNUAL MEAN			3.44
HIGHEST DAILY MEAN	118	Nov 12	176
LOWEST DAILY MEAN	.04	Aug 31	.05
ANNUAL SEVEN-DAY MINIMUM	.06	Aug 20	.05
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK FLOW			368
INSTANTANEOUS PEAK STAGE			4.68
INSTANTANEOUS LOW FLOW			.05
ANNUAL RUNOFF (CFSM)	1.16	1.36	.00
ANNUAL RUNOFF (INCHES)	15.74	18.49	1.13
10 PERCENT EXCEEDS	11	11	15.37
50 PERCENT EXCEEDS	1.4	1.5	10
90 PERCENT EXCEEDS	.19	.10	.78
			.06

Figure 14. Reproduction of Lost Creek page from the USGS's *Water Resources Data - Ohio, 1993 Water Year*.

Figure 15. Annual and seasonal variations in discharge and in loads of sediments and nutrients exported from Lost Creek Watershed.

Table 7. Comparisons of annual runoff for the Lost Creek Watershed and for other northwestern Ohio watersheds.

Year	Lost Cr.	Tiffin R.	Auglaize R.	Blanchard R.	Maumee R.	Portage R.	Honey Cr.	Rock Cr.	Sandusky R.
1982	31.34	15.98	15.63	16.60	17.07	18.28	16.09		16.89
1983	24.27	14.03	8.56	7.49	11.40	10.06	9.05		7.89
1984	19.7	13.30	18.43	18.89	14.12	19.50	17.16	18.95	23.58
1985	22.67	14.63	7.91	7.79	10.49	9.93	9.33	8.71	9.35
1986	17.33	14.30	16.72	12.33	14.12	13.45	14.39	15.33	15.67
1987	11.03	8.13	8.37	8.92	8.14	7.58	10.81	10.41	11.90
1988	14.78	8.69	4.88	4.32	6.34	4.47	4.40	4.55	5.06
1989	11.7	14.26	9.61	7.49	10.41	11.23	8.52	9.02	9.18
1990	18.45	13.97	15.50	12.33	13.02	10.97	13.10	11.91	14.68
1991	18.86	13.87	14.08	12.93	13.24	13.76	11.27	13.10	14.51
1992	12.31	9.45	14.62	13.05	12.43	13.52	10.85	12.91	11.80
1993	18.49	19.53	16.82	16.16	18.40	18.61	17.24	17.82	17.37
Ave In.	18.41	13.34	12.59	11.53	12.43	12.61	11.85	12.20	13.16
Pd of Record	82-93	22 - 93	21-93	24-93	30-93	28-93	77-93	84-93	24-93
POR Ave.	18.41	11.04	11.79	10.07	10.71	10.53	12.05	12.2	11.05

classification means that less than 95% of the values would be within 15% of the true value.

Given the construction of a trapezoidal flume at the outlet of the watershed, it is unfortunate that the quality of the discharge measurements only ranks as fair. With the installation of a flume, the relationship between stage and discharge should be constant and the accuracy of the discharge should be excellent. Instead, the stage-discharge relationships have apparently changed considerably during the course of the study. In Table 8, the discharge associated with various stages are listed for the theoretical rating curve of the flume (number 1), as provided by the Agricultural Research Service, and for the successive rating curves used by the USGS (numbers 2-6), as based on their discharge measurements. Data in the table indicate that the USGS rating curves indicate much higher discharges at given stages in the flume than does the theoretical rating curve. Furthermore, the successive rating curves of the USGS are "U" shaped, with ratings #2 and #6 having lower discharges at a given stage than ratings #3-#5. One possible explanation offered by the USGS for the large shift between ratings #5 and #6 is that the flume has settled, changing its shape and slopes.

The various rating curves have a substantial impact on both the calculated discharge and on the calculated loads of nutrients exported from the watershed. To illustrate these impacts, the discharges and total phosphorus loads for the 1986 to 1993 period were calculated using either successive rating curves #2-#6, as phased in by the USGS, or using rating #6 for the entire period. These values are taken from the observed discharge and observed flux columns of the flow ratio program, so they utilize exactly the same stages and concentrations to calculate discharges and loads, but used different rating tables. The results of the comparisons are shown in Figures 16 and 17. Use of rating curve #6 would have resulted in substantially lower discharges and loads in each year. Combining data from all the years, the discharges based on the successive ratings and used in this report were 22% higher than if rating #6 had been applied throughout the period. Similarly, the total phosphorus export was 18% higher than it would have been if rating #6 were applied throughout the study period.

The USGS plans to take a new set of measurements on the flume geometry and calculate a new theoretical rating for the flume, to compare with the measured discharges (Harold Shindel, USGS, Columbus, Ohio, personal communication, June 1994). The shifting of the rating curves coupled, with the divergence between the theoretical and measured curves

Table 8. Comparison of discharge at given stages for the theoretical rating curve and for five successive rating curves (curves #2 - #6) used by the USGS.

Rating Curve	-----Cubic feet per second discharge, at indicated stages-----				
	1.00 ft	2.00 ft	3.00 ft	4.00 ft	5.00 ft
ARS	0.000	9.35	57.00	164.0	351.2
USGS #2	0.001	13.20	74.00	211.0	490.0
USGS #3	0.000	14.00	92.00	243.0	470.0
USGS #4	0.000	14.00	92.00	243.0	470.0
USGS #5	0.004	15.42	92.00	243.0	470.0
USGS #6	0.062	10.87	71.83	212.8	460.0

Figure 16. Effects of rating curves on calculated discharge (A) and total phosphorus loads (B) for water years 1986-1993.

Figure 17. Number of pesticide samples analyzed per month during the period of record (A) and monthly average TWMCs of major herbicides (B).

and the unusually high unit area discharges for the watershed all raise questions regarding the discharge data for the station.

It should be noted that the discharges reported for the 1982-1985 water years, as shown in Figure 15 and in the appendices, are based on the USGS rating number 2 rather than on the theoretical rating curve (Baker, 1988a). All flow data in the report, as well as the associated loading data, are based on the USGS rating curves and their associated beginning dates for use.

B. Nutrient and Sediment Concentrations

The average time weighted and flow weighted concentrations of nutrients and sediments in Lost Creek over the period of record are shown in Table 4. Because the sampling frequency varies with flow conditions in the stream, ranging from hourly samples during high flow to daily samples during low flow, the calculation of average concentration in the stream is not accomplished by the standard calculation of averages. In the standard calculation of the average concentration, the sum of the concentrations in individual samples would be divided by the number of samples, as indicated in formula 1. In streams, it is useful to know the average concentration of substances, as would be experienced by organisms living in the stream or by water supplies withdrawing water from the stream at a constant rate. To determine such an average from sampling programs with variable frequencies, it is necessary to weight each sample by the time interval that it is used to characterize the stream. The procedure for calculating this time weighted mean concentration (TWMC) is shown in formula 2, where the sum of the products of concentration x time is divided by the sum of the time.

$$\text{Formula 1 Average Concentration} = \frac{c_i}{n}$$

$$\text{Formula 2 Time Weighted Mean Concentrations} = \frac{c_i t_i}{t_i}$$

$$\text{Formula 3 Flow Weighted Mean Concentration} = \frac{c_i q_i t_i}{q_i t_i}$$

Where c_i , q_i and t_i and n are, respectively, the concentration in the i th sample, the instantaneous discharge at the time the i th sample was collected, the duration of time the i th sample is used to characterize the stream, and the total number of samples collected during the time interval for the averages.

In streams, it is also of interest to calculate the average concentration as seen by a receiving body of water, such as a lake or a downstream section of the river. From the standpoint of a receiving body of water, a concentration associated with a high flow rate is more important than a concentration associated with a low flow rate. For characterizing the pollutant loading to a receiving water or export from a watershed, the relevant average concentration is the flow weighted mean concentration (FWMC) as calculated using formula 3. For each sample it is necessary to take into account its concentration, the interval of time that it is used to characterize the stream, and the stream discharge associated with that time interval. The flow weighted average concentration essentially involves dividing the total load of a pollutant by the total volume of water that carried that pollutant load to the receiving waters.

The relationship between the TWMC and the FWMC is an important characteristic and varies among various parameters. If, on average, the concentration of a pollutant increases with increasing flow, the FWMC will be higher than the TWMC. Such is the case for suspended solids and the nutrient parameters from Lost Creek (Table 9). Substances whose concentrations increase with increasing flow are typically derived from nonpoint sources and are carried into the stream by runoff water. If point sources were the major source of these nutrients and sediments, concentrations would increase with decreasing flow, since the dilution of the point source inputs would decrease as stream flows decrease.

In Lost Creek the TWMCs are higher than the FWMCs for chloride, sulfate, silica, and conductivity (Table 9). In this case the higher TWMCs than FWMCs reflect the higher concentrations of dissolved substances in base flow derived primarily from groundwater than in surface runoff.

Annual variations in the TWMCs and in FWMCs in the Lost Creek Watershed are shown in Tables 10 and 11. The TWMCs for each year were obtained by running the nutrient concentration exceedency program, while the annual flow weighted mean concentrations were obtained from the annual loading and discharge data as presented in the appendix. It is evident that both the TWMCs and FWMCs vary significantly from year to year.

To characterize pollutant concentrations in streams, information on the distribution of concentrations is also very important. In Table 12, the TWMC, the median, maximum and minimum concentrations, and the concentrations exceeded 90%, 95% and 99% of the time

Table 9. Average annual concentrations, average annual loads, and average unit area loads for nutrient and sediment parameters exported from the Lost Creek Watershed during the period between October 1, 1981 through September 30, 1993.

Parameter	Number of samples	Time weighted mean conc. mg/L	Flow weighted mean conc. mg/L	Average annual load m tons/yr	Average annual load short tons/yr	Unit area load kg/ha	Unit area load lbs/acre
Suspended sediments	6563 (78%)	66.8	271.7 296.3	1394	1536	1272	1135
Total Phosphorus	6561 (78%)	0.158	0.474 0.502	2.43	2.68	2.22	1.98
Soluble Reactive Phosphorus	6591 (78%)	0.021	0.047 0.046	0.241	0.27	0.22	0.20
Nitrate + Nitrite Nitrogen	6624 (78%)	2.78	3.76 3.69	19.3	21.26	17.61	15.71
Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen	6555	1.11	2.17 2.25	11.17	12.31	10.19	9.09
Ammonia Nitrogen	6556	0.09	0.21				
Chloride	6619	18.1	12.50 12.33	64.1	70.6	58.5	52.17
Sulfate	3164 (43%)	50.6	23.5				
Silicate (SiO ₂)	6554 (78%)	7.73	6.73				
Conductivity (µmhos)	6247						

Table 10. Annual variations in the TWMC of nutrients and sediments at the Lost Creek monitoring station for the water years from 1982 to 1993.

-----Time Weighted Mean Concentrations, mg/L-----							
Year	Number of Samples	Suspended Solids	Total Phosphorus	Soluble Reactive Phosphorus	Nitrate + Nitrite Nitrogen	Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen	Chloride
1982	531	270	0.332	0.030	2.80	1.59	18.9
1983	808	197	0.301	0.023	1.96	1.44	16.9
1984	406	76	0.184	0.023	2.42	1.10	18.6
1985	464	58	0.140	0.011	2.83	0.97	17.6
1986	744	69	0.155	0.014	3.23	1.31	21.7
1987	507	40	0.114	0.028	2.45	1.26	20.6
1988	437	41	0.119	0.015	2.76	1.01	19.9
1989	541	38	0.189	0.029	3.44	1.09	17.2
1990	495	53	0.130	0.014	2.74	1.03	18.5
1991	529	56	0.149	0.020	2.32	0.96	15.0
1992	629	42	0.118	0.016	2.67	0.88	16.8
1993	536	54	0.143	0.024	2.05	0.96	15.8

Table 11. Annual variations in the FWMC of nutrients and sediments at the Lost Creek monitoring station for the water years from 1982 to 1993.

-----Flow Weighted Mean Concentrations, mg/L-----							
Year	Number of Samples	Suspended Solids	Total Phosphorus	Soluble Reactive Phosphorus	Nitrate + Nitrite Nitrogen	Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen	Chloride
1982	435	293	0.449	0.046	2.79	1.87	11.7
1983	746	367	0.593	0.057	3.31	2.49	13.3
1984	297	182	0.412	0.062	4.22	2.00	11.5
1985	455	283	0.477	0.030	3.59	2.00	13.1
1986	742	336	0.567	0.029	4.78	2.76	15.6
1987	504	209	0.414	0.076	4.95	2.71	16.3
1988	427	296	0.521	0.035	4.61	2.19	13.1
1989	481	256	0.376	0.025	5.38	2.15	13.4
1990	495	295	0.480	0.037	4.30	2.41	11.6
1991	529	273	0.525	0.058	2.85	2.10	9.5
1992	622	161	0.375	0.053	3.99	1.80	12.6
1993	535	211	0.408	0.052	2.36	1.95	10.8

Table 12. Distribution of nutrient and sediment concentrations in Lost Creek for the period of record.

Parameter	----- Concentrations, mg/L-----					
	Time Weighted Mean	Median	90 th Percentile	95 th Percentile	99 th Percentile	Maximum
Suspended sediment	66.782	16.6	87.7	212.6	1108.3	13744
Total phosphorus	0.158	0.078	0.304	0.502	1.340	15.010
Soluble reactive phosphorus	0.021	0.011	0.049	0.069	0.132	3.002
Nitrate + nitrite N	2.784	2.070	5.660	7.690	13.280	30.100
Total Kjeldahl nitrogen	1.113	0.850	1.870	2.558	5.480	30.460
Ammonia	0.089	0.041	0.148	0.237	0.640	890.000
Chloride	18.091	17.700	25.300	27.800	33.700	222.700
Sulfate	50.574	58.200	97.200	111.100	135.200	467.000
Silica	7.732	7.630	10.540	11.470	14.450	996.000
Conductivity	549.036	583	700	746	825	2593

are listed for sediment and nutrient parameters. The above summaries of concentrations are for the period of record at the Lost Creek station.

In Appendix A, the concentrations of suspended solids, total phosphorus, soluble reactive phosphorus, nitrate + nitrite nitrogen, and conductivity are shown for individual samples in the form of annual chemographs for each water year. The annual hydrographs are also shown for each water year.

C. Nutrient and Sediment loads

In Appendix A, monthly and annual loads of sediments and nutrients are shown for each water year of the study (1982 - 1993). The data in the appendix were derived using the flow ratio program (Figure 7) for each parameter and each water year. For periods when samples were not available, concentrations were estimated as described in the methods section. A high flow ratio and low number of samples collected indicate those months in which monthly loads were manually adjusted to provide a better estimate of loading.

The average annual sediment and nutrient loads for the period of record are shown in Table 9. The total loads and the unit area loads are shown in both metric and English units. Two values of FWMCs are shown for each parameter. The upper value is derived from the annual loads as shown in the appendix. As such, they include the estimated concentrations for periods when concentration data were not available. The lower value is based on the flux program (Figure 4) and therefore does not contain estimated values.

The extent of annual variations in discharge and in loads of sediments and nutrients are shown in Figure 15. In general, years with high annual discharges had high loads of sediments and phosphorus. In contrast, nitrate export did not closely follow annual discharge. The largest discharges and loads occurred in the early years of the study.

D. Pesticide Concentrations

Pesticide monitoring at the Lost Creek station was initiated in 1983. A total of 719 samples have been analyzed for pesticides at the sampling station during the period of record. The sampling program was focused on the spring and early summer runoff events following pesticide applications associated with planting operations. The monthly distribution of the sampling program is shown in Figure 17.

As has become evident in midwestern pesticide monitoring programs, highest concentrations occur during runoff events following pesticide application. The pattern of monthly average herbicide concentrations is shown in Figure 17. These graphs combine all of the samples in a particular month over the entire period of record. For alachlor, atrazine and metolachlor, the highest monthly concentrations occurred in June. Alachlor concentrations were also high in May, but dropped off quickly in July and August, and were rarely detected in other months. For both atrazine and metolachlor, high concentrations were also present in May and July, and both of these persisted at low concentrations throughout the year.

The concentration distributions of major herbicides over the period of record are shown in Table 13. Atrazine had the highest TWMC, followed by metolachlor, alachlor, cyanazine and metribuzin in that order. The long term TWMC was below the drinking water standards for all monitored pesticides. Peak concentrations of atrazine, alachlor and metolachlor were 68, 65, and 64 ppb ($\mu\text{g/L}$) respectively. The median concentration was below the detection limit for all herbicides except atrazine, which had a median concentration of 0.02 ppb.

E. Pesticide Loads

The annual pesticide loads exported from the Lost Creek Watershed for 1983 - 1993 are shown in Table 14 and in Figure 18. These loads were calculated using the automated Beale Ratio Estimator method, as developed by the WQL under a current grant from the Great Lakes National Program Office of the U.S. EPA. Pesticide loads are even more variable from year to year than are nutrient and sediment loads. For example, the export of atrazine ranged from 0.2 kg in 1991 to 11.0 kg in 1984. Because these herbicides breakdown more quickly and/or become less subject to transport, the timing of rainfall following application has a much greater impact on pesticide export than on nutrient export. The large annual variability in loading makes it particularly difficult to identify trends in relation to the adoption of pesticide best management practices.

Table 13. Distribution of herbicide concentrations in Lost Creek for the period of record.

Parameter	----- Concentrations, µg/L-----					
	Time Weighted Mean	Median	90 th Percentile	95 th Percentile	99 th Percentile	Maximum
Atrazine	0.787	0.020	1.431	3.197	13.984	68.395
Alachlor	0.322	0.000	0.251	0.826	8.164	64.943
Metolachlor	0.439	0.000	0.958	2.075	7.449	63.643
Cyanazine	0.288	0.000	0.188	0.779	9.273	23.144
Metribuzin	0.133	0.000	0.131	0.419	2.473	25.151

Table 14. Loads of major herbicides transported from the Lost Creek watershed annually. Loads are given in kilograms per year, \pm the 95% confidence interval.

Year	Alachlor	Atrazine	Metolachlor	Cyanazine	Metribuzin
1983	5.767 \pm 1.076	8.877 \pm 1.237	3.558 \pm 0.930	2.456 \pm 0.255	2.185 \pm 0.521
1984	4.662 \pm 1.682	10.962 \pm 0.870	2.764 \pm 0.757	4.039 \pm 0.759	0.648 \pm 0.064
1985	0.015 \pm 0.011	2.593 \pm 0.217	1.172 \pm 0.211	0.157 \pm 0.030	0.080 \pm 0.055
1986	2.321 \pm 0.699	10.519 \pm 1.382	5.361 \pm 0.289	1.307 \pm 0.276	1.255 \pm 0.191
1987	4.167 \pm 1.222	8.922 \pm 2.139	5.573 \pm 0.903	3.418 \pm 0.838	0.917 \pm 0.204
1988	0.022 \pm 0.004	0.377 \pm 0.071	0.215 \pm 0.039	0.156 \pm 0.309	0.172 \pm 0.423
1989	0.150 \pm 0.042	1.703 \pm 0.208	2.131 \pm 0.313	0.265 \pm 0.267	0.075 \pm 0.050
1990	0.845 \pm 0.165	3.143 \pm 1.078	3.034 \pm 0.842	0.191 \pm 0.356	0.207 \pm 0.055
1991	0.008 \pm 0.082	0.205 \pm 0.267	0.233 \pm 0.657	0.000 \pm 0.000	0.018 \pm 0.099
1992	1.165 \pm 1.358	0.965 \pm 0.706	1.191 \pm 0.596	0.427 \pm 0.149	0.801 \pm 0.598
1993	5.884 \pm 1.301	5.996 \pm 1.146	11.058 \pm 2.282	0.985 \pm 0.810	0.277 \pm 0.074

Figure 18. Variations in annual loads of herbicides exported from the Lost Creek Watershed

Part 5. DISCUSSION: TRENDS IN LOST CREEK DATA

A. Trends in Management Practices

Examination of the available data on tillage management practices indicates that the amount of no-till within the watershed increased dramatically during the initial demonstration project, peaking in 1983 and 1984 at about 20% of the cropland. In 1984, reduced tillage of various forms was used on another 15% of the cropland. In addition, cover crops were used on 28% of the cropland.

Following the conclusion of the demonstration project, the amounts of no-till decreased to the point where, in 1987, it was used on only about 4% of the cropland. Chisel plowing was used on about 25% of the cropland in that year while about 20% of the land was plowed.

Beginning in 1990, the amounts of no-till increased rapidly through 1992, at which time about 32% of the crops were grown using no-till. Chisel plowing was used on another 14% of the cropland, only 6% of the land was plowed. Another 27% of the land was enrolled in the CRP program. Wheat, oats and hay covered 17% of the cropland. Fully 90% of the cropland was being treated with some type of management to reduce erosion.

It is noteworthy that in the initial demonstration program, sizable incentives were used to gain farmer adoption of no-till, but in the 1990 -1992 period, similar incentives were not available. The components of the farm bill aimed at improving water quality were very effective in gaining conservation measures in the watershed.

Given the high level of treatment within the watershed in 1992, it would be of considerable interest to continue the tracking of management practices beyond the current 319 program to see if the high level of conservation treatment continues.

The short duration of chemical tracking in the watershed, coupled with the annual variations in crops grown make analysis of trends in chemical usage beyond the scope of the current report.

B. Trends in Pollutant Loading

Trends in annual discharge and in both the loads and FWMCs of sediments and nutrients are shown in Figure 19. The statistical significance of the trends is shown in Table 15.

The data indicate that significant downward trends occurred for discharge, sediment loads, total phosphorus loads and nitrate loads. The trend line also decreases for soluble reactive phosphorus, but the decrease is not statistically significant. Although the trend lines for the FWMCs of suspended sediment, total phosphorus and nitrates are negative (i.e., downward) none of these declines are statistically significant.

The downward trends in pollutant loads are not only statistically significant, but the slopes indicate that the amounts of decrease in loading were also rather large. These can be estimated by examining the intercepts of the trend lines for 1981 in comparison with 1994. For example, the sediment load would have decreased from approximately 2100 metric tons per year to about 700 metric tons per year. Nitrate export would have decreased from 25 metric tons to 12 metric tons.

These results indicated that the decreased loads of sediment, total phosphorus and nitrate were associated with decreased water runoff rather than with any decrease in the concentrations of these substances in the water. This contrasts markedly with recent trend studies of our laboratory for other northwestern Ohio streams (Richards and Baker, 1993). At other stations, we found that there were no significant decreases in discharge, but instead, we observed very significant decreases in the concentrations of nutrients in the streams. These analyses involved compensation for the effects of flow and season on monthly FWMCs and consequently were more rigorous than the trend analyses used in the current study.

Interpretation of the downward trends in nutrient loading hinges on the explanation of the downward trends in discharge at this station. Comparison of the discharge data for other northwestern Ohio USGS gauging stations over the 1982 - 1993 period indicates upward sloping trend lines (Figure 20), but in no cases were the upward trends significant. Consequently, for USGS gauging stations in this region, Lost Creek is unique in terms of having a significant downward trend in discharge.

Figure 19. Trends in annual discharge and in loadings and FVMCs for sediment and nutrients exported from the Lost Creek Watershed

Table 15. Explained variance, trend slope, and statistical significance of trend slope for loads and flow-weighted mean concentrations

Variable	r ²	trend slope [†] (mg/L/yr)	t-ratio	probability	significance [‡]
Discharge	.392	-.281	-2.54	.0293	*
Loads					
Suspended Solids	.426	-117.297	-2.73	.0213	*
Total Phosphorus	.413	-.166	-2.65	.0243	*
Sol. React. Phosphorus	.087	-.010	-0.98	.3526	
Nitrate + Nitrite	.696	-.997	-4.79	.0007	***
FWMCs					
Suspended Solids	.200	-7.686	-1.58	.1447	
Total Phosphorus	.128	-.007	-1.21	.2540	
Sol. React. Phosphorus	.007	.0004	0.27	.7967	
Nitrate + Nitrite	.002	-.011	0.13	.8964	

[†] Trend slope units for discharge are million cubic meters/day/year

[‡] *: .01<p<.05; **: .001<p<.01; ***: p<.001, where p is probability

Figure 20. Discharge trends at northwestern Ohio stream gages during the 1982-1993 period.

The following possibilities exist to explain the observed discharge trend at Lost Creek.

1. The downward trend is an artifact of errors in discharge measurements.

As noted earlier, there have been significant changes in the rating tables used for discharge calculation at the Lost Creek station. In particular, there was a major change between rating #5 and #6. Had rating #6 been used in 1992, instead of rating #5, the discharge could have been as much as 30% lower. Similarly, if rating #5 had been used in 1993, the discharge would have been about 30% higher. All of the USGS rating curves yielded discharges that were much higher than the theoretical rating for the flume. It should also be noted that there was a change in the method of stage measurement in 1985. If the decreased discharge is really an artifact of errors in discharge measurement, then the decreased nutrient and sediment loading did not really occur and no reductions in loading could be attributed to adoption of conservation measures in the watershed.

2. The downward trend is due to localized rainfall patterns in the Lost Creek Watershed.

For small watersheds, localized intense rainfall patterns can yield runoff amounts that are atypical of regional patterns. Thus the downward trend in discharge for Lost Creek could be real, but it could also be simply a consequence of rainfall patterns in the watershed. If variations in rainfall patterns are the cause of the downward trend in discharge, then the decreased pollutant loading is not attributable to adoption of conservation measures.

3. The downward trend is a consequence of changes in runoff associated with adoption of conservation measures.

With adoption of conservation measures such as no-till and conversion to cover crops and CRP lands, greater proportions of the precipitation inputs may be infiltrating into the soil and less water may runoff the surface. Since Lost Creek purportedly has less intensive tile systems than other areas of northwestern Ohio, more water infiltrating into the soil may be recharging ground water and less may return to the streams via tile flow. It is also possible that the transpiration losses associated with CRP land and cover crops reduces overall runoff from the land. If

adoption of conservation measures such as those in Lost Creek do result in decreased runoff, then such benefits must be factored into programs aimed at assessing the benefits of conservation measures. Most current programs focus on detecting trends in pollutant concentrations rather than in runoff and loading.

At the present time, it is uncertain which of the above, or what combination of the above, account for the observed trend data. The USGS will be conducting further investigations of the ratings at the Lost Creek station. Some rainfall data had been collected in the Lost Creek Watershed and it may shed some light on possible causes of decreased discharge.

The above trend analysis is based on annual loads and no adjustments have been made on the effects of discharge on flow weighted concentrations. A more detailed analysis of trend data, such as that employed by Richards and Baker (1993) should be conducted for this station. The more detailed procedure involves use of monthly flow and concentration data and adjusts the data for variations in monthly flow and for seasonal effects. With more detailed analysis, trends in FWMCs might be revealed.

It is possible that adoption of conservation measures such as those in the Lost Creek watershed could alter flow pathways and decrease the percent of rainfall leaving the watershed as runoff. Certainly these measures are known to increase infiltration. Documenting the benefits of decreased runoff would involve different research and monitoring strategies than simply looking for decreases in pollutant concentrations. It would involve detailed rainfall measurements within the watershed coupled with application of hydrological models.

One method to examine data for trends in flow weighted concentration is to use double mass curves (Hindall, 1989). The results of such analyses are shown in Figure 21. In this technique, the cumulative load of a pollutant is plotted against the cumulative discharge. A change in the slope of the curve would reflect a change in the flow weighted concentration. The data plotted in Figure 21 is taken from the monthly discharge and loading data in the Appendix to this report. Changes in slope for total phosphorus are not evident, confirming the conclusion that the flow weighted concentrations of phosphorus have not changed. In the case of nitrate, the slope of the double mass curve is rather wavy, but certainly major changes in slope are not evident.

Figure 21. Double mass curves for the export of total phosphorus and nitrate for the Lost Creek Watershed.

Part 6. DISCUSSION: COMPARISON OF LOST CREEK WITH NEARBY WATERSHEDS

A. Comparisons of FWMCs and Unit Area Loads

Water quality monitoring similar to that in Lost Creek has been underway in several other agricultural watersheds of northwestern Ohio. These watersheds are listed in order of increasing size in Table 16. Lost Creek (4.23 square miles) has the smallest watershed, while the Maumee River (6,330 square miles) has the largest. In the table, the average runoff in inches is shown for the time period corresponding to the studies in Lost Creek. As noted previously (Table 7), the average annual runoff from Lost Creek is much higher than that of the other monitored watersheds.

The FWMCs of suspended solids, total phosphorus, and total Kjeldahl nitrogen (organic nitrogen plus ammonia) are all higher in Lost Creek than in the other four watersheds. Nitrate concentrations are relatively low in Lost Creek and Rock Creek in comparison with the Maumee and Sandusky Rivers and Honey Creek. The concentrations of soluble reactive phosphorus in Lost Creek are considerably higher than in Rock Creek but somewhat lower than at the other stations.

The combination of higher discharge and higher FWMCs make the unit area yields of all five of these parameters much higher than at the other stations, particularly for sediments and sediment associated pollutants. The unit area sediment yield for Lost Creek is 72% higher than for Rock Creek, which has the next highest unit area sediment yield. The unit area yield of total phosphorus for Lost Creek is 66% higher than that of the Sandusky River, which has the second highest per acre yield of phosphorus. The yield of total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN) in Lost Creek is 70% higher than that of the Maumee River, which had the second highest TKN yields. Unit area nitrate yields from the watershed were higher than for other watersheds, even though the extent of tile drainage in the watershed is thought by local agricultural officials to be low relative to the Sandusky and Maumee basins.

If the downward trends in pollutant yields in Lost Creek, as described in the previous section, are due to adoption of agricultural BMPs in the watershed, then presumably the

Table 16. Comparisons of discharge, flow weighted mean concentrations, and unit area yields for northwestern Ohio rivers.

Parameter	Lost Cr.	Rock Cr.	Honey Cr.	Sandusky R.	Maumee R.
Area, mi ²	4.23	34.6	149	1251	6330
Unit Area Discharge, inches	18.42	12.20	11.85	13.16	12.43
FWMC, mg/L					
suspended sediment	271.7	222.6	156.5	195.1	237.0
total phosphorus	0.474	0.387	0.377	0.392	0.445
sol. reactive phosphorus	0.047	0.032	0.053	0.053	0.058
nitrate + nitrite-N	3.76	3.35	5.36	5.00	5.73
total Kjeldahl nitrogen	2.17	1.77	1.72	1.69	1.88
Unit Area Yields (lbs/acre/yr)					
suspended sediment	1135	659	434	600	544
total phosphorus	1.98	1.14	1.04	1.19	1.16
sol. reactive phosphorus	0.200	0.095	0.134	0.151	0.187
nitrate + nitrite-N	15.71	9.91	14.5	15.4	14.3
total Kjeldahl nitrogen	9.09	5.23	4.65	5.19	5.35

*For the Maumee River the unit area yields are taken from data covering 1976-1991.

unit area yields for Lost Creek would have been even higher if the pollution abatement programs had not occurred.

It is noteworthy that the watersheds of both Lost Creek and Rock Creek occupy terminal moraines and, as such, would be expected to have higher erosion rates and pollutant yields. The proportion of cropland in each is similar. Even though the Lost Creek watershed has been the site of two major agricultural pollution abatement programs, and the Rock Creek watershed has not had any special programs, the unit area pollutant yields for Lost Creek are much higher than for Rock Creek.

There are several possible explanations of the high unit area pollutant yields from the Lost Creek watershed. The implications of the high yields for water quality management programs in northwestern Ohio hinge on which of the explanations most closely reflects the actual situation in the watershed. Several explanations and their associated implications are listed below.

1. The high calculated yields of nutrients and sediments could be a consequence of overestimates of the discharge.

If the discharge estimates are high, then the high unit area yields are likewise overestimates of actual yields. Consequently, there are no particular implications for area pollution abatement programs since the yields may not actually be higher than for other areas. The implications from study would relate more to the difficulties in obtaining accurate discharge data for small watersheds by incorporating them into the standard cooperative stream gauging program of the USGS. Small watersheds may simply require special efforts to obtain accurate ratings in relatively short periods.

2. The high yields could reflect unit area yields characteristic of the terminal moraines in this region.

If the observed yields for Lost Creek are representative of the yields from terminal moraines in the Maumee watershed, then these terminal moraines would be particularly important as pollutant sources areas in the Maumee watershed. Since the Lost Creek watershed has yields that are much higher than the average yields for the Maumee watershed of which it is a part, then the yields for other portions of the

Maumee watershed must be much lower than average. This conclusion assumes that pollutant delivery from various regions within the watershed to the Maumee monitoring station is similar. The results would provide strong support for targeting control programs related to sediment and phosphorus to areas of terminal moraines.

3. The high yields could reflect more efficient pollutant delivery from smaller watersheds than from larger watersheds.

It is frequently observed that sediment delivery ratios decrease as watershed size increases (Boyce, 1975). Consequently, the high yields from the Lost Creek Watershed could relate more to the small size of the watershed than to higher erosion rates and associated higher movement of pollutants off fields and into streams. One would need to compare watersheds of similar size but draining lands from ground moraines or from Lake Plane soils to evaluate the importance of targeting in this region. The lower unit area yields at the mouth of the Maumee River would be related to transport losses within the stream/flood plane system. Pollutants originating in different positions in the Maumee watershed could be affected in varying degrees. Among the implications of this explanation would be the need for much more detailed studies of sediment transport through drainage networks in order to support appropriate targeting of control measures in large river basins.

A watershed project was initiated in Ottawa county in which monitoring was attempted in a pair of watersheds of similar size to Lost Creek, but which drained Lake Plain soils. Unfortunately, difficulties in discharge measurements and unstable rating curves precluded use of the resulting data for loading calculations (WQL unpublished data). That study also underscored the difficulties in obtaining discharge data in small watersheds.

B. Watershed Scale Effects

Even with uncertainties in the discharge measurements in Lost Creek, the Lost Creek data have helped to reveal several important scale effects related to watershed size (Baker 1988b; 1993). Some of scale effects are listed below:

1. Small watersheds have more discrete runoff events per year than do larger watersheds.
2. Peak pollutant concentrations during runoff events are higher in small watersheds than in large watersheds.
3. Intermediate pollutant concentrations persist for shorter periods of time in small watersheds than in large watersheds.
4. In small watersheds the amount of time during which a fixed percent of the total loading (e.g., 90%) occurs is much shorter than in larger watersheds.
5. Larger numbers of samples are needed to characterize loading from a small watershed than from a large watershed.

Part 7. DISCUSSION: SOME LESSONS LEARNED

The Lost Creek projects began in 1981. The sciences of watershed management and watershed studies have undergone considerable evolution during the course of these studies. Certainly, if the studies were to be started over, many things would be done differently. To help others possibly avoid some of the problems that currently complicate interpretation of data from the Lost Creek projects, and possibly to set the stage for future work in this watershed, a review of how the program might be structured differently seems appropriate.

A. Tracking watershed management practices

1. Track all relevant management practices in the watershed, not just the acres where BMPs have been adopted through project efforts - In the early years of the program acres of no-till and of chisel plow were recorded, but the status of tillage in the vast majority of the watershed was not recorded. Were fall or spring plowing used on all acres that weren't in wheat or under no-till or reduced till? Only in the latter years of the project were efforts made to specifically describe the management practices on all acres of the watershed. Since the runoff response of the watershed to rainfall inputs reflects the conditions over the whole watershed, correlating water quality and loading data with watershed conditions requires information on the entire watershed.
2. Track and/or characterize the entire watershed each year, rather than variable portions of the total watershed. - During the 1986 to 1992 period, the number of acres for which information was available varied greatly. We did not know if the monitored acres were representative or biased relative to conditions in the entire watershed.
3. Track ground cover, not just tillage practice. The hydrological response and erosion within the watershed are more directly impacted by ground cover than by tillage practice. Both are important and should be recorded.
4. Persons doing the tracking should be involved in converting the tracking data into appropriate data summaries for the watershed. - Where difficulties arise in converting field notes into the desired watershed summaries, such as pounds of

pesticide active ingredients applied in the watershed, involvement of those who recorded the field data could help resolve the difficulties and avoid similar difficulties in the future.

5. Summarize tracking data annually. - The tracking data should be summarized as quickly as possible rather than four or five years after the data were collected. If the tracking data are summarized shortly after collection, missing data could be identified and gaps filled.

6. Tracking should be linked to a geographical information system (GIS). - Although maps with numbered fields are available for each year of the Lost Creek Watershed studies, the data were not entered into a GIS system. Thus, it is not possible to conveniently analyze the spatial distributions of various management practices in the watershed or to identify the location of missing data. Using a GIS system could also have helped identify critical erosion areas and supported field level targeting within the watershed.

B. Discharge measurements

1. Accurate discharge data are essential for research watersheds. - In any study involving measurements of pollutant loading, accurate discharge data are required. Obtaining such data for watersheds in the size range of the Lost Creek Watershed is particularly difficult. Runoff events are typically of such short duration that getting a crew to the site to make discharge measurements is difficult. Installation of flumes of sufficient size to handle peak discharges is also difficult. Planning for obtaining and somehow validating discharge data should be one of the most important parts of program planning. It should also be a critical factor in watershed selection for demonstration projects. If there are no good sites for discharge measurements, alternative locations for the study should be considered.

2. For research projects in small watersheds, incorporation of the watershed into the standard Cooperative Stream Gauging Program of the USGS may not provide sufficient resources to quickly obtain reliable data. Special arrangements with the USGS, ARS or other groups with experience in stream gauging will likely be required.

C. Project Management

1. Someone needs to be responsible for overseeing the entire project. - Watershed projects typically involve a variety of groups conducting various aspects of the project. Someone needs to be sure that all components of the study are progressing in a timely fashion. In the case of the 319 project in Lost Creek, no group was clearly identified as having responsibility for the whole project. With turnover in the offices of the Defiance SWCD, those operating the study were not the same people who were involved in submitting the proposal and originally planning the study. A major shortfall of funds for the study was not recognized until very late in the study period. The missing funds were precisely the funds that would have supported overall project management, data integration and preparation of a final report.

Part 8. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusions

1. BMP adoption in the Lost Creek Watershed

Programs to gain farmer adoption of BMPs in the Lost Creek Watershed were successful. However, following the initial program in 1981-1984, which focused on cash incentives for adoption of no-till, many farmers reverted to conventional till practices. The second program to foster BMP adoption utilized various components of the 1988 and 1992 Farm Bill. It resulted in even more adoption of conservation measures in the watershed. By 1992, the amount of treatment in the watershed had reached a very high level. It remains to be seen if farmers will revert to less treatment following the conclusion of this project and/or expiration of components of the Farm Bill programs.

2. Trends in discharge and in export of nutrients and sediment

Statistically significant downward trends in discharge and in the loading of suspended sediments, total phosphorus and nitrate were observed during the course of these studies. The downward trends in nutrient and sediment loading were related to the downward trend in discharge rather than to a decrease in flow weighted concentrations. If the land management changes of the type occurring in Lost Creek actually modify the hydrological response of the watershed to rainfall inputs, then programs designed to assess the water quality benefits need to incorporate measurements to document this effect. Programs that focus on looking for decreased pollutant concentrations could miss the benefits of the conservation measures.

3. Magnitude of nutrient and sediment export from the Lost Creek Watershed

Even though high levels of conservation treatment were attained in the Lost Creek Watershed, and even though significant downward trends were observed during the study, the average annual unit area yields of sediments and nutrients from the watershed were very high in comparison to the Maumee River Watershed, as a whole, and in comparison to other monitored watersheds in northwestern Ohio.

The high yields were related to both high concentrations of nutrients and sediments and to the high runoff volumes from the Lost Creek Watershed. These high yields could underscore the importance of the terminal moraine areas as critical pollutant source areas in northwestern Ohio tributaries to Lake Erie. The high yields could also reflect a scale effect associated with watershed size. As the smallest of our study watersheds, the high yields may reflect a high pollutant delivery ratio to the watershed outlet. The management implications of these two different explanations for the high pollutant yields from the Lost Creek Watershed are very different.

4. Uncertainties in the Lost Creek discharge data

In the above conclusions, the discharge data have been taken at face value. It should be noted that a certain amount of uncertainty is associated with the discharge measurements at that site. The USGS rating curves, upon which the discharge data are based, result in much higher discharges than the theoretical rating curve provided by the ARS when the flume was constructed. Furthermore, the USGS rating curves have changed markedly during the study. Such changes would have to be explained by changes in the shape and slope of the flume or by changes in the downstream channel that affect water levels in the flume. The existing data indicate that the runoff from the Lost Creek Watershed is much higher than for surrounding watersheds. Is higher runoff from terminal moraines a characteristic of this region, or is there unusually high ground water discharge in the watershed, or is the higher runoff an artifact in bias in the rating curves? The answer to this question has major implications on the interpretation of the Lost Creek data and on its implications for watershed management in the Lake Erie Basin. The USGS does plan to take measurements on the flume and recalculate a theoretical rating curve.

B. Recommendations

1. Discharge measurements for the Lost Creek Watershed should continue, with special efforts to verify the accuracy of the rating curves. Since stream gauging is underway in few gauging stations in this size range in Ohio, the USGS has continued to monitor discharge for the 1994 Water Year.
2. The watershed currently has a very high level of land treatment. Will this level of treatment continue beyond the study period or will farmers revert to more

conventional tillage programs with less residue? Continued tracking of the watershed would reveal the current degree of farmer commitment to no-till production in this region.

3. If the high level of treatment achieved by 1992 continues within the watershed, then continued water quality monitoring could clarify the levels of pollutant export from areas of terminal moraines that can be expected using current BMPs. Such information would be very useful in on-going water quality management planning within the Lake Erie Basin.

4. While there are some gaps in the tracking records for this watershed, and there is some uncertainty regarding discharge measurements, there is never-the-less an exceptional amount of data available for the Lost Creek Watershed. It is very possible that some of the missing data can be retrieved. Past aerial photography or satellite imagery could also be used to fill in missing crop and residue data. Some of the uncertainty regarding the discharge may be resolved as the USGS continues work at the gauging station. With all the information available for this watershed, it could serve as an excellent location for model testing and evaluation.

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Table A-1. Monthly loads and discharge for the Lost Creek Tributary for water year 1982. Discharge is given in million cubic meters, and loads are given in metric tons.

Month	USGS Discharge	Flow Ratio	N of Samples	SS	TP	SRP	NO23	TKN	Cl
October	0.63	1.408	60	99	0.26	0.069	2.5	1.26	12.4
November	0.13	1.231	26	2	0.01	0.003	0.3	0.12	3.3
December	0.12	2.766	12	18	0.04	0.004	0.4	0.18	2.8
January	0.74	2.045	24	136	0.28	0.050	4.0	1.46	14.4
February	0.64	1.205	28	13	0.08	0.039	1.3	0.59	9.7
March	4.12	1.030	145	951	1.63	0.154	6.5	6.60	33.3
April	1.03	2.061	13	350	0.55	0.026	2.8	2.41	10.9
May	0.30	---	0	159	0.22	0.013	1.7	1.13	4.3
June	0.17	7.210	24	51	0.06	0.004	1.0	0.37	2.9
July	0.78	1.062	103	765	0.75	0.038	3.7	2.10	7.5
August	0.04	---	0	7	0.01	0.003	0.1	0.07	0.3
September	0.03	---	0	4	0.01	0.002	0.1	0.05	0.3
Totals	8.72		435	2554	3.92	0.403	24.3	16.34	102.0

Figure A-1. Annual hydrograph, sedigraph, and nutrient chemographs for Lost Creek (USGS 04185440) during the 1982 water year.

Table A-2. Monthly loads and discharge for the Lost Creek Tributary for water year 1983. Discharge is given in million cubic meters, and loads are given in metric tons.

Month	USGS Discharge	Flow Ratio	N of Samples	SS	TP	SRP	NO23	TKN	Cl
October	0.02	14.033	2	5	0.01	0.002	0.1	0.04	0.3
November	0.90	0.989	134	127	0.40	0.112	2.7	1.61	19.4
December	1.17	1.065	97	153	0.52	0.073	2.4	2.14	17.6
January	0.19	8.734	5	33	0.06	0.006	0.7	0.33	3.6
February	0.55	1.112	59	32	0.13	0.023	1.6	1.06	8.4
March	0.64	1.143	91	116	0.21	0.019	2.7	1.11	9.7
April	1.55	1.046	163	402	0.80	0.055	3.9	3.25	13.7
May	0.93	0.879	77	496	0.68	0.040	1.9	2.93	6.8
June	0.54	1.050	86	954	1.02	0.037	4.6	3.52	6.8
July	0.18	1.564	22	152	0.17	0.011	1.7	0.66	2.6
August	0.04	25.250	4	7	0.01	0.003	0.1	0.07	0.7
September	0.04	24.291	6	5	0.01	0.003	0.1	0.06	0.4
Totals	6.76		746	2480	4.01	0.383	22.4	16.79	90.0

Figure A-2. Annual hydrograph, sedigraph, and nutrient chemographs for Lost Creek (USGS 04185440) during the 1983 water year.

Table A-3. Monthly loads and discharge for the Lost Creek Tributary for water year 1984. Discharge is given in million cubic meters, and loads are given in metric tons.

Month	USGS Discharge	Flow Ratio	N of Samples	SS	TP	SRP	NO23	TKN	Cl
October	0.02	3.883	11	5	0.01	0.002	0.1	0.05	0.3
November	0.40	546.423	1	56	0.15	0.021	2.3	0.78	6.8
December	0.87	1.410	13	73	0.28	0.052	2.7	1.09	8.7
January	0.06	10.170	6	10	0.02	0.002	0.2	0.10	0.8
February	1.11	1.062	35	95	0.30	0.090	3.1	1.44	9.8
March	1.14	1.125	72	315	0.61	0.070	5.2	3.29	12.5
April	1.01	1.197	69	161	0.41	0.033	4.5	1.78	9.7
May	0.56	1.174	42	187	0.34	0.051	3.2	1.70	10.4
June	0.08	3.231	9	18	0.02	0.002	0.4	0.15	1.3
July	0.04	8.107	10	20	0.02	0.002	0.2	0.13	0.6
August	0.04	13.769	8	5	0.01	0.002	0.1	0.06	0.3
September	0.14	0.839	21	52	0.09	0.011	1.1	0.40	2.0
Totals	5.48		297	997	2.26	0.339	23.1	10.97	63.2

Figure A-3. Annual hydrograph, sedigraph, and nutrient chemographs for Lost Creek (USGS 04185440) during the 1984 water year.

Table A-4. Monthly loads and discharge for the Lost Creek Tributary for water year 1985. Discharge is given in million cubic meters, and loads are given in metric tons.

Month	USGS Discharge	Flow Ratio	N of Samples	SS	TP	SRP	NO23	TKN	Cl
October	0.44	1.119	40	49	0.18	---	4.3	0.96	7.5
November	0.68	1.116	50	82	0.24	---	3.6	1.33	10.9
December	0.84	1.072	63	110	0.30	---	3.8	1.50	16.6
January	0.57	3.584	13	88	0.17	---	2.1	0.94	7.7
February	1.34	1.114	45	136	0.37	---	2.6	1.84	8.7
March	1.65	0.859	64	1147	1.44	---	4.1	4.72	24.0
April	0.64	1.082	40	125	0.25	---	1.4	1.03	5.3
May	0.06	17.127	8	31	0.04	---	0.3	0.21	0.9
June	0.02	1.678	19	3	<0.01	---	0.1	0.03	0.3
July	0.01	1.085	39	6	<0.01	---	<0.1	0.02	0.2
August	0.03	0.936	39	7	0.01	---	0.2	0.05	0.5
September	0.02	1.473	35	1	<0.01	---	0.1	0.03	0.3
Totals	6.31		455	1783	3.01	---	22.7	12.64	82.9

Figure A-4. Annual hydrograph, sedigraph, and nutrient chemographs for Lost Creek (USGS 04185440) during the 1985 water year.

Table A-5. Monthly loads and discharge for the Lost Creek Tributary for water year 1986. Discharge is given in million cubic meters, and loads are given in metric tons.

Month	USGS Discharge	Flow Ratio	N of Samples	SS	TP	SRP	NO23	TKN	Cl
October	0.20	1.132	60	38	0.10	0.007	2.2	0.50	4.4
November	0.93	1.145	78	138	0.36	0.026	7.0	1.80	18.8
December	0.53	0.988	61	108	0.25	0.004	2.2	0.99	7.9
January	0.15	1.217	46	8	0.03	0.003	0.6	0.25	3.0
February	0.77	1.090	91	87	0.22	0.010	2.2	1.10	9.3
March	1.06	1.132	109	303	0.60	0.038	3.3	3.35	13.1
April	0.15	1.061	39	17	0.04	0.004	0.5	0.19	3.0
May	0.06	0.211	80	63	0.08	0.004	0.4	0.36	1.2
June	0.26	1.359	58	288	0.36	0.004	2.2	1.57	4.8
July	0.59	1.617	57	544	0.65	0.032	2.1	2.90	8.4
August	0.02	0.307	23	16	0.02	<0.001	<0.1	0.08	0.2
September	0.10	1.322	40	13	0.04	0.008	0.2	0.22	1.3
Totals	4.82		742	1621	2.73	0.139	23.0	13.29	75.4

Figure A-5. Annual hydrograph, sedigraph, and nutrient chemographs for Lost Creek (USGS 04185440) during the 1986 water year.

Table A-6. Monthly loads and discharge for the Lost Creek Tributary for water year 1987. Discharge is given in million cubic meters, and loads are given in metric tons.

Month	USGS Discharge	Flow Ratio	N of Samples	SS	TP	SRP	NO23	TKN	Cl
October	0.96	5.374	19	224	0.49	0.119	3.8	2.31	11.6
November	0.26	0.972	49	12	0.06	0.017	1.0	0.50	5.7
December	0.33	1.309	46	18	0.09	0.011	1.1	0.65	6.9
January	0.14	0.912	28	7	0.03	0.004	0.6	0.17	2.8
February	0.22	0.915	32	6	0.05	0.018	0.8	0.43	3.7
March	0.28	0.816	54	53	0.10	0.012	1.4	0.91	4.4
April	0.14	0.962	34	5	0.02	0.004	0.4	0.23	2.5
May	0.49	0.862	80	206	0.29	0.030	3.9	2.37	8.6
June	0.08	0.915	47	30	0.04	0.005	1.2	0.24	1.6
July	0.15	0.610	53	79	0.11	0.012	0.8	0.50	1.9
August	0.01	1.157	28	<1	<0.01	<0.001	<0.1	0.01	0.1
September	0.01	0.438	34	<1	<0.01	<0.001	<0.1	0.01	0.2
Totals	3.07		504	642	1.27	0.232	15.2	8.33	50.0

Figure A-6. Annual hydrograph, sedigraph, and nutrient chemographs for Lost Creek (USGS 04185440) during the 1987 water year.

Table A-7. Monthly loads and discharge for the Lost Creek Tributary for water year 1988. Discharge is given in million cubic meters, and loads are given in metric tons.

Month	USGS Discharge	Flow Ratio	N of Samples	SS	TP	SRP	NO23	TKN	Cl
October	0.02	0.756	36	2	0.01	0.003	0.2	0.06	0.8
November	0.24	1.040	58	43	0.10	0.017	2.4	0.43	5.3
December	1.36	0.855	78	171	0.50	0.068	8.1	1.93	19.0
January	0.13	1.006	34	7	0.03	0.005	0.4	0.19	2.0
February	0.82	1.006	43	33	0.14	0.019	3.0	0.98	12.0
March	0.71	1.458	46	222	0.34	0.013	2.9	1.88	9.2
April	0.78	0.967	83	741	1.03	0.017	2.0	3.51	5.2
May	0.02	0.987	31	<1	<0.01	<0.001	<0.1	0.01	0.4
June	<0.01	1.054	18	<1	<0.01	<0.001	<0.1	<0.01	0.1
July	<0.01	---	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
August	0.01	---	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
September	0.02	---	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Totals	4.11		427	1219	2.14	0.142	19.0	8.99	53.9

Figure A-7. Annual hydrograph, sedigraph, and nutrient chemographs for Lost Creek (USGS 04185440) during the 1988 water year.

Table A-8. Monthly loads and discharge for the Lost Creek Tributary for water year 1989. Discharge is given in million cubic meters, and loads are given in metric tons.

Month	USGS Discharge	Flow Ratio	N of Samples	SS	TP	SRP	NO23	TKN	Cl
October	.30	1.015	40	173	0.14	0.007	1.7	0.81	3.3
November	.61	0.856	44	35	0.13	0.021	5.5	0.92	11.2
December	.30	2.259	35	55	0.12	0.012	1.5	0.54	4.5
January	.75	0.889	44	270	0.34	0.021	3.5	1.84	8.3
February	.10	0.657	33	7	0.02	<0.001	0.4	0.12	1.5
March	.27	0.805	39	105	0.16	0.001	1.2	0.90	3.7
April	.37	0.948	38	130	0.22	0.011	2.1	0.97	3.3
May	.16	0.927	44	30	0.06	0.003	0.6	0.37	2.5
June	.35	0.486	98	29	0.06	0.003	0.9	0.49	4.7
July	.03	1.488	37	1	0.01	0.002	0.1	0.03	0.5
August	<.01	0.404	10	<1	<0.01	<0.001	<0.1	<0.01	<0.1
September	.01	0.941	19	<1	<0.01	<0.001	<0.1	0.01	0.1
Totals	3.26		481	834	1.26	0.082	17.5	7.00	43.8

Figure A-8. Annual hydrograph, sedigraph, and nutrient chemographs for Lost Creek (USGS 04185440) during the 1989 water year.

Table A-9. Monthly loads and discharge for the Lost Creek Tributary for water year 1990. Discharge is given in million cubic meters, and loads are given in metric tons.

Month	USGS Discharge	Flow Ratio	N of Samples	SS	TP	SRP	NO23	TKN	Cl
October	0.01	0.931	33	<1	<0.01	<0.001	<0.1	0.01	0.3
November	0.11	1.198	34	4	0.02	0.001	1.1	0.18	3.2
December	0.01	0.769	34	<1	<0.01	<0.001	<0.1	0.01	0.2
January	0.58	---	0	114	0.20	0.020	2.2	1.08	7.7
February	1.45	---	0	127	0.36	0.051	4.9	1.99	19.8
March	0.47	1.099	43	119	0.26	0.017	2.3	1.97	6.1
April	0.52	0.975	57	82	0.18	0.010	2.0	1.25	4.8
May	0.83	1.078	62	603	0.80	0.028	4.5	3.11	8.2
June	0.14	0.947	55	96	0.09	0.007	1.2	0.45	2.0
July	0.33	1.049	62	151	0.21	0.014	2.6	0.95	3.0
August	0.64	1.195	82	217	0.34	0.041	1.4	1.35	3.5
September	0.03	1.625	32	1	<0.01	0.001	<0.1	0.02	0.6
Totals	5.13		494	1514	2.46	0.190	22.1	12.37	59.3

Figure A-9. Annual hydrograph, sedigraph, and nutrient chemographs for Lost Creek (USGS 04185440) during the 1990 water year.

Table A-10. Monthly loads and discharge for the Lost Creek Tributary for water year 1991. Discharge is given in million cubic meters, and loads are given in metric tons.

Month	USGS Discharge	Flow Ratio	N of Samples	SS	TP	SRP	NO23	TKN	Cl
October	0.70	1.006	45	105	0.31	0.071	2.5	1.30	6.0
November	0.23	1.834	37	13	0.05	0.009	0.8	0.34	4.0
December	1.81	0.920	53	551	1.19	0.116	3.9	3.91	14.6
January	0.47	1.069	37	54	0.16	0.024	1.1	0.73	5.0
February	0.40	0.957	52	51	0.13	0.026	1.1	0.57	5.6
March	0.32	0.799	53	47	0.07	0.010	1.0	0.61	5.3
April	1.03	0.804	99	565	0.75	0.037	2.6	2.92	4.3
May	0.15	0.973	27	37	0.07	0.006	1.0	0.44	2.6
June	0.09	0.802	35	9	0.02	0.004	1.0	0.20	2.1
July	0.01	0.850	30	<1	<0.01	<0.001	<0.1	0.01	0.2
August	0.01	1.025	29	<1	<0.01	<0.001	<0.1	0.01	0.1
September	<0.01	0.298	32	<1	<0.01	<0.001	<0.1	<0.01	<0.1
Totals	5.25		529	1433	2.76	0.302	14.9	11.04	49.7

Figure A-10. Annual hydrograph, sedigraph, and nutrient chemographs for Lost Creek (USGS 04185440) during the 1991 water year.

Table A-11. Monthly loads and discharge for the Lost Creek Tributary for water year 1992. Discharge is given in million cubic meters, and loads are given in metric tons.

Month	USGS Discharge	Flow Ratio	N of Samples	SS	TP	SRP	NO23	TKN	Cl
October	0.39	0.863	48	79	0.18	0.055	1.8	0.88	4.8
November	0.33	0.859	41	56	0.16	0.025	1.4	0.79	5.3
December	0.27	0.924	61	26	0.09	0.013	1.1	0.48	4.2
January	0.26	1.310	32	9	0.04	0.006	1.2	0.28	4.7
February	0.48	0.943	51	43	0.12	0.021	2.2	0.64	6.1
March	0.54	1.016	99	53	0.15	0.010	1.9	0.74	5.6
April	0.57	1.180	63	193	0.33	0.020	1.2	1.39	3.9
May	0.12	0.994	36	6	0.02	0.002	0.5	0.15	2.4
June	0.07	0.849	54	16	0.02	0.001	0.4	0.13	1.6
July	0.15	0.900	54	30	0.05	0.006	1.4	0.19	2.2
August	0.01	0.535	36	<1	<0.01	<0.001	<0.1	<0.01	0.2
September	0.24	0.925	47	42	0.11	0.021	0.5	0.49	2.3
Totals	3.43		622	553	1.28	0.180	13.7	6.17	43.1

Figure A-11. Annual hydrograph, sedigraph, and nutrient chemographs for Lost Creek (USGS 04185440) during the 1992 water year.

Table A-12. Monthly loads and discharge for the Lost Creek Tributary for water year 1993. Discharge is given in million cubic meters, and loads are given in metric tons.

Month	USGS Discharge	Flow Ratio	N of Samples	SS	TP	SRP	NO23	TKN	Cl
October	0.18	0.787	41	58	0.16	0.044	0.3	0.47	3.1
November	1.15	1.254	40	233	0.52	0.078	2.6	2.41	12.5
December	0.62	0.895	61	191	0.32	0.017	0.8	1.30	4.3
January	1.05	16.900	6	195	0.34	0.035	3.8	1.87	13.5
February	0.04	0.754	32	<1	<0.01	<0.001	0.1	0.02	0.7
March	1.00	0.937	71	177	0.34	0.060	1.4	1.92	7.5
April	0.58	1.069	64	181	0.30	0.015	0.8	1.33	4.4
May	0.13	0.739	48	19	0.04	0.002	0.2	0.24	1.1
June	0.24	0.990	70	28	0.07	0.014	1.5	0.36	4.9
July	0.13	1.012	30	4	0.01	0.003	0.5	0.10	2.7
August	0.01	0.683	36	<1	<0.01	<0.001	<0.1	<0.01	0.1
September	0.03	0.874	36	2	0.01	0.002	0.1	0.04	0.6
Totals	5.15		535	1088	2.10	0.269	12.1	10.05	55.4

Figure A-12. Annual hydrograph, sedigraph, and nutrient chemographs for Lost Creek (USGS 04185440) during the 1993 water year.

T 916

Field No. 4

Acres: 28

Cooperator: Gary Pierce Phone: _____

MAP: _____

1992 Crop (circle one): Corn Beans Wheat Oats Hay Other: _____

Primary Tillage Method (circle one): Plow Chisel Offset-disc Disc F. Cultivate
No-till Other: Soil Finisher

Date Primary Tillage performed: 5-14

Secondary Tillage (indicate # of times with each implement):
____ Disc _____ F. Cultivator _____ Harrowgator _____ Drag
____ Cultimulcher _____ Roterra 1X Other Soil Finisher

Planting Date: 5-15

Fertilizer Applied:

Date:	Analysis:	Amount: (lbs)	Method of Application (Row, Broadcast, Preplant Sidedress, etc.)	N lbs/Ac.	P ₂ O ₅ lbs/Ac.	K ₂ O lbs/Ac.
Examples:						
4/30/92	0-23-30	400	Broadcast	0	46	120
5/30/92	82-0-0	225	Sidedress	184.5	0	0
<u>5-14</u>	<u>0-13-37</u>	<u>150</u>	<u>R worked</u>	<u>0</u>	<u>20</u>	<u>59</u>
<u>5-15</u>	<u>8-32-16</u>	<u>200</u>	<u>In Row</u>	<u>16</u>	<u>64</u>	<u>32</u>
<u>6-14</u>	<u>82-0-0</u>	<u>102</u>		<u>100</u>		
_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____

Figure B-1a. Example of land management data sheet from Lost Creek watershed, front.

Insecticides:			
Date:	Name of Insecticide:	Rate:	Application Method: (seed treatment, banded, in-furrow, broadcast)

Herbicides:		Formulation:		Application Method: (Banded, Surface, Incorporated)	
Date:	Name of Herbicide:	Liquid - L Wettable Powder - WP Dry Flowable - DF	Rate:		
Example:					
5/30/92	Sencor	DF	4 lb.	Surface	
5-16	Bicep	6L	3qt.		
7-6	Accent			Spot Spray	

Figure B-1b. Example of land management data sheet from Lost Creek watershed,